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Abstract

Methods for the assessment of digital health technologies (DHTs) are not currently standardised, and DHTs pose new challenges for traditional health technology assessment (HTA) methods. The ASSESS-DHT manual presents a systematic and standardised approach for the assessment of DHTs, and is intended to serve two purposes: firstly, to support health technology developers (HTDs) through the assessment process; and to support HTA bodies assessing DHTs across Europe.

This is an interim version of the ASSESS-DHT manual. This version of the manual collates deliverables and interim work from ASSESS-DHT and has been developed in collaboration with partners across the ASSESS-DHT consortium. It provides guidance and tools on DHT challenge areas to support the piloting activities to take place in the second half of the project. The manual provides guidance on conducting assessments of DHTs with different characteristics and at different stages of their life cycle. Topics covered include areas traditionally assessed in HTA such as safety, effectiveness and cost-effectiveness and also specialist topic considerations such as cybersecurity, AI, data protection and data quality.

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI-CDSS	AI-based clinical decision support systems
AMA	American Medical Association
AQuAS	Agency for Quality and Assessment of Catalonia
BfArM	German Federal Institute for Drugs and Medical Devices
BSI	Bundesamt für Sicherheit in der Informationstechnik
CCPA	California Consumer Privacy Act
CWE	Common Weakness Enumeration
DHT	Digital health technology
DiGAs	Digital health applications as defined according to the German Regulation “Digitale Gesundheitsanwendungen-Verordnung – DiGAV
DiGAV	Digitale Gesundheitsanwendungen-Verordnung (German Regulation on DiGAs)
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DTAC	Digital Technology Assessment Criteria
EEA	European Economic Area
EHDS	European Health Data Space
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
EU	European Union
EUDAMED	European Database on Medical Devices
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information System
HAS	Haute Autorité de Santé
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (United States of America)
HTA	Health technology assessment
HTAR	Regulation (EU) 2021/2282 on Health Technology Assessment
HTD	Health technology developer
ICD	International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems
ICER	Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IMDRF	In Vitro Diagnostics Regulation
IQR	Interquartile Range
ISO	International Organization for Standardization

IVD	In Vitro Diagnostics
IVDR	In Vitro Diagnostics Regulation
JCA	Joint Clinical Assessment
MAR	Missing at random
MCAR	Missing completely at random
MDD	Medical Device Directive
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
MFA	Multi-Factor Authentication
MHRA	Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
NMAR	Not missing at random
OWASP	Open Web Application Security Project
PHR	Personal Health Record
PHTI	Peterson Health Technology Institute
PLV-RWD	Pre-deployment localised external validation using real-world data
QALY	Quality-Adjusted Life Year
RCT	Randomised controlled trial
RWD	Real world data
SaMD	Software as Medical Device
SBOM	Software Bill of Materials
SIMD	Software in a Medical Device
SMPC	Secure Multi-Party Computation
SQL	Structured Query Language
SROI	Social Return on Investment
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
UKCA	United Kingdom Conformity Assessed
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Digital health technologies (DHTs) promise the ability to radically change the delivery of high-quality, timely and effective care across Europe, with wide-reaching impact on all aspects of the health and care system. However, processes for the assessment of DHTs currently vary depending on who is responsible for the assessment. This poses challenges both for the assessor, and for the health technology developer (HTD) when providing evidence for assessment. Additionally, DHTs pose a new challenge for the traditional methods of health technology assessment (HTA) as they require consideration of more specialist issues than traditional, non-digital health technologies, such as cybersecurity and data management. The ASSESS-DHT project aims to develop a systematic and standardised approach to the assessment of DHTs to improve processes across Europe.

The ASSESS-DHT manual is an overarching document that describes work completed in the ASSESS-DHT project and aims to support HTDs and HTA agencies. This version of the manual is an interim version that collates ongoing work in ASSESS-DHT for testing in the piloting phase of the project. The manual draws on a variety of sources, including existing European and International frameworks for the assessment of evidence, other deliverables within the ASSESS-DHT project, and the synthesised experience and findings of HTA partners involved in the project through workshops and meetings.

For HTDs, the manual provides support regarding the methodological approach to assessment of DHTs, with requirements for the evidence that should be provided for assessments. For HTA agencies, the manual provides guidance to support the assessment process. Topics covered in the manual include describing the assessment context, evaluation safety, effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of any given DHT and support for considering specialist areas including data protection, data quality, cyber security and AI. The manual highlights how assessment considerations vary depending on the characteristics of the DHT and its life cycle stage.

1 Introduction

1.1 ASSESS-DHT framework

ASSESS-DHT is a research project funded through Horizon Europe that aims to increase the adoption of trustworthy and effective digital health technologies (DHTs) across Europe. A focus of the project is on developing robust and harmonised methodologies for health technology assessment (HTA) of DHTs. The ASSESS-DHT framework and manual is one of the deliverables supporting this objective.

The ASSESS-DHT framework includes four components, as illustrated in the figure below:

- A taxonomy
- A lifecycle evaluation
- Assessment context
- DHT assessment considerations for different HTA domains
- Specialist topics

Figure 1. The ASSESS-DHT Framework

The taxonomy and lifecycle evaluation support HTA agencies to understand how assessment considerations change for different types of DHT and depending on the DHT's lifecycle stage. The taxonomy and lifecycle evaluation are initial phases of the assessment process and link to the considerations and specialist topics described in the chapters that follow.

The interim manual consists of six domains related to the assessment context and considerations which are described below.

Table 1. Manual domains

Domain	Description	Link in manual
Health problem and current use of the DHT	Describes the target condition, target population, epidemiology and the availability and patterns of use of the technology in question	Health problem and current use of the DHT
Description and technical characteristics of the DHT	Describes the DHT, including its functions, design and technical characteristics	Description and technical requirements of the DHT
Regulatory aspects	Describes the regulation of DHTs and supports understanding of their need to be compliant with relevant regulations	Regulatory aspects
Safety	Assessment of unwanted or harmful effects caused by using a DHT	Safety
Clinical efficacy and effectiveness	Assessment of whether a DHT can work under ideal conditions (efficacy) and whether the DHT works in practice (effectiveness)	Clinical efficacy and effectiveness
Economic aspects	Assessment of costs and economic impact associated with the DHT	Costs and economic evaluation

For each domain there are topics and issues for consideration in an HTA (shown in the figure below) with accompanying evidence requirements and methodological considerations. The framework content is informed by ASSESS-DHT activities including literature reviews, detailed analysis of EU policy documents and direct engagement and consensus building with DHT experts.

Figure 2. Description of the framework hierarchy

Assessment considerations are arranged in HTA domains aligned to classical areas of HTA and specialist topics focussing on digital specific aspects often not routinely considered in HTA but which may be critical to the assessment of DHTs.

Table 2. Specialist topics

Topic	Description	Link in manual
Data protection and privacy	Assessment of data protection and privacy as defined by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	Data protection and privacy
Data quality	A data quality framework including assessment criteria for data quality management and 9 core dimensions of data quality.	Data quality
Cyber security	A high-level cybersecurity assessment checklist to address the challenges of fragmentation in cybersecurity standards and requirements across the EU	Cybersecurity
AI	Three AI-specific checklists to support specific aspects of evaluation	Artificial Intelligence (AI)
Human Factors	Guidance on the interaction with, use and usability of DHTs	Human Factors
Information management	Data management and storage	Information management
Interoperability	Connection to other software, devices or health systems	Interoperability

1.2 How to use the ASSESS-DHT framework and manual

The ASSESS-DHT manual is designed as a supplement to the EUnetHTA Core model, which is a common reference framework used for HTA. The EUnetHTA Core model was not designed for use in assessment of DHTs, and therefore the ASSESS-DHT framework and manual have been developed to provide further guidance and focus on issues and specific considerations relevant to the assessment of DHTs.

This manual is designed to support both HTA bodies and DHT developers in preparing evidence and materials for assessment of DHTs and is intended to be used alongside other HTA documents and resources, such as those produced by the ASSESS-DHT project. Additional resources are referenced in each chapter of the manual.

2 Health Technology Assessment

HTA is a multidisciplinary process that uses explicit methods to determine the value of a health technology at different points in its lifecycle. The purpose is to inform decision-making to promote an equitable, efficient, and high-quality health system (O'Rourke et al., 2020). HTA responds to a jurisdiction-specific policy question and primarily aims to assess the clinical effectiveness and the value for money of the new intervention compared to existing practice. Other areas of consideration may include patient, social, legal, equality and diversity impact of the technology and any relevant local or national considerations.

There are four overarching procedural stages that typically define the HTA process:

- Scoping – definition of the research question and issues for consideration
- Collection of evidence – either by the HTA agencies or provided as a submission by the health technology developer (HTD)
- Evaluation of the evidence – technical evaluation of the evidence by the HTA agency
- Appraisal and decision making – consideration of the technology in light of the technical evaluation and other relevant factors to make a decision about whether the health technology should be used in the healthcare system see section 2.3

These stages are described in further detail in the next sections of this chapter.

2.1 Scoping

The scoping process defines the research questions that will be used as the basis for HTA by establishing what will and will not be included in the assessment. Scoping provides a framework for the assessment by defining the issues for consideration and establishing both standards of evidence to be included and any relevant boundaries for the assessment. The scope of the assessment will be finalised before requesting data from developers or manufacturers. Because of variations in clinical practice, the scope of assessment in one jurisdiction can vary from that in another jurisdiction.

The PICO framework as developed by Richardson et al (1995) is the most widely used framework in HTA, and defines the following elements captured in the table below:

Table 3. The PICO framework (Adapted from CASP-UK)

Element	Research Question
Population / Patient	The population or patient group of interest to the assessment
Intervention	The intervention of interest to the assessment
Comparator / Control	The comparator, or the control intervention (if applicable)
Outcome(s)	The outcomes that are of interest to the assessment and their respective measurement methods – e.g. quality of life, progression-free survival

2.2 Collection of evidence

HTA agencies sometimes collect the evidence themselves to inform HTA, sometimes use evidence that has been submitted by the HTD and sometimes combine both approaches in an evidence request from the HTD complemented by evidence searches undertaken by the agency. The decision to use one or other approach depends on the resources and expertise in the agency, time available for the assessment, stakeholder engagement, legislation underlying the process, and agency preferences.

Resources are available for HTA agencies to consider their evidence requirements:

- For the EU HTA joint clinical assessment (JCA), there is a dossier submitted by the HTD which should include relevant information on regulatory approval, and relevant uses of the technology.
- ASSESS-DHT includes a general checklist of information (Annex to be added to final manual following the completion of ASSESS-DHT WP5) that HTA agencies can use to inform their evidence requests for HTDs and their own searches of the evidence.
- The domain chapters and specialist topics in the ASSESS-DHT manual contain evidence requirements that can be used and adapted to support evidence requests.

2.3 Evaluation, appraisal and decision making

HTA evaluates the identified evidence within the scope defined at the start of the HTA process. Not all HTA agencies have the same remit and responsibility and therefore the issues agencies assess and the depth to which they assess them can vary. Some HTA agencies evaluate only relative effectiveness and value for money, whereas others may have some regulatory or payer responsibilities. A distinction is made between assessment, appraisal and decision making. HTA agencies will undertake assessment, (that is technical evaluation of the evidence), but will not always be responsible for appraisal (that is the considerations around the importance of the issues identified) and decision making. Similarly, the status of decisions may vary between countries, depending on whether the recommendations of an HTA are binding or non-binding. The ASSESS-DHT manual highlights considerations for assessors of DHTs allowing HTA agencies to identify which considerations are important for the technology under assessment within their jurisdiction.

2.4 References

O'Rourke, B., Oortwijn, W. and Schuller, T. (2020) "The new definition of Health Technology Assessment: A milestone in international collaboration", *International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care*, 36(3), pp. 187–190. doi:10.1017/s0266462320000215.

Richardson, W.S. *et al.* (1995) "The well-built clinical question: A key to evidence-based decisions", *ACP Journal Club*, 123(3). doi:10.7326/acpjc-1995-123-3-a12.

3 Taxonomy of DHTs

3.1 Rationale for a taxonomy

The diversity of DHTs means that there can be variation in the assessment approach that needs to be applied to DHTs with different characteristics. Taxonomies can support the HTA process by defining criteria which place DHTs into different categories with distinct assessment and evidence requirements.

The ASSESS-DHT taxonomy was developed by examining various classification, categorisation, and grouping schemes used for different purposes to develop a taxonomy for DHTs that is suitable for:

- ▶ Highlighting the extent to which HTA is necessary for different DHT categories,
- ▶ Characterising assessment requirements.

For the latter, the categories need to be broad enough to encompass a wide range of DHTs, yet specific enough to highlight the assessment and evidence requirements for each domain.

The ASSESS-DHT taxonomy presents a conceptual model for the landscape of DHTs. It has been produced early in the project to guide the identification of considerations for DHT assessment and will be revised following piloting. The taxonomy was developed using different methodologies including search and review of existing taxonomies for DHTs, scoping review of frameworks for assessing DHTs, and a survey to HTA agencies. These methods are detailed in WP2 Deliverable 2.1: Taxonomy of DHT for assessment purposes.

3.2 Description of the ASSESS-DHT taxonomy

Definition of DHTs for HTA purposes

The ASSESS-DHT taxonomy aims to classify DHTs according to different criteria suitable for HTA purposes across Europe. To achieve this, the taxonomy aligns its definition of DHTs with the definition of software as defined by the Regulation (EU) 2017/745 on Medical Devices (MDR). For this taxonomy, DHTs are defined as software as a medical device (SaMD) or software in a medical device (SiMD), depending on the role of the software in the overall function of the DHT. To be appropriate for ASSESS-DHT assessment, the software must be intended by the manufacturer to be used, alone or in combination, for at least one of the following specific medical purposes:

- ▶ diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction, prognosis, treatment or alleviation of disease
- ▶ diagnosis, monitoring, treatment, alleviation of, or compensation for, an injury or disability
- ▶ investigation, replacement or modification of the anatomy or of a physiological or pathological process or state.

This definition of DHTs excludes digital technologies that are intended for monitoring or managing lifestyle habits and well-being purposes, even though they may impact health. The definition also excludes digital technologies that are intended for general non-medical purposes, even where they are used in a healthcare setting.

3.3 Components of the taxonomy

The taxonomy is built using a set of criteria designed to facilitate HTA of DHTs across Europe. It focuses on three main areas: (medical) purpose, DHT-relevant dimensions of “risk”, and the use of artificial intelligence (AI).

(Medical) Purpose

There is considerable variation in the intended medical purpose and application of any single DHT, which presents unique challenges from an HTA perspective. The intended medical purpose and application of a DHT can influence the types of evidence that are required (or acceptable) for assessing their effectiveness, and more fundamentally also dictates the outcomes for which evidence is required.

The purpose of the DHT should therefore determine the outcome(s) of interest to the assessment (e.g., diagnostic vs therapeutic). The taxonomy proposes a differentiation between the following five purposes: i) prevention, ii) monitoring, iii) prediction/prognosis, iv) diagnosis, v) treatment.

Under the taxonomy, alleviation of disease and compensation for injury or disability are considered part of the treatment purpose. DHTs without a medical application or purpose (for e.g., operational purposes of hospitals) are not included in the taxonomy as they are outside of scope.

Risk

The function or purpose of the DHT combined with the risk to the user (vulnerability of patients in terms of state of healthcare situation/condition) is considered to play a direct role in determining the level of evidence needed to judge the balance of risk and benefits of using a specific DHT. These can then be used to inform specific evidence standards and assessment requirements. The taxonomy combines directness and vulnerability criteria from the International Medical Device Regulators Forum (2014) into a 3x3 matrix, resulting in four evidence requirement levels based on the level of risk (see table below).

Table 4. Taxonomy risk matrix

Vulnerability of patients (state of healthcare situation/condition)	“Directness” Intention of using DHT-collected or -produced information for health care decisions (by health care provider or patient)		
	Make (treat or diagnose)	Drive (clinical) management	Inform (clinical) management
Critical	IV Provides information to treat or diagnose a disease or conditions in a critical situation or condition → very high impact on patient or public health	III Provides information to drive clinical management of a disease or conditions in a critical situation or condition → high impact on patient or public health	II Provides information to inform clinical management of a disease or conditions in a critical situation or condition → medium impact on patient or public health
Serious	III Provides information to treat or diagnose a disease or conditions in a serious situation or condition → high impact on patient or public health	II Provides information to drive clinical management of a disease or conditions in a serious situation or condition → medium impact on patient or public health	I Provides information to inform clinical management for a disease or conditions in a serious situation or condition → low impact on patient or public health
Non-serious	II Provides information to treat or diagnose a disease or conditions in a non-serious situation or condition → medium impact on patient or public health	I Provides information to drive clinical management of a disease or conditions in a non-serious situation or condition → low impact on patient or public health	I Provides information to inform clinical management for a disease or condition in a non-serious situation or condition → low impact on patient or public health

Artificial Intelligence

The increase in AI-enabled DHTs, and the extent to which they autonomously perform specific tasks is of specific concern to the ASSESS-DHT project. The EU regulatory framework for AI-enabled DHTs is governed by the EU AI Act (2024) and the Medical Device Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2017/745), which provides requirements and obligations regarding the specific use of AI for developers and deployers. Systems are categorised into risk levels ranging from unacceptable to low/minimal – AI-enabled DHTs are likely to fall into classes IIa-III based on function and risk (Regulation (EU) 2017/745).

The HTA approach must consider the risk of AI components in DHTs. AI-specific assessment elements are still under development, and challenges such as continuous learning AI must be considered. The ASSESS-DHT framework differentiates between DHT based on static and adaptive AI components to derive evidence requirements that apply to the respective group (see table 5).

Table 5. AI taxonomy

AI component	Definition	Source	Examples
Static (also fixed or locked)	Using fixed algorithms that respond in a predictable way: if input does not change, output will be the same each time Operate based on predefined rules and processes that do not dynamically adapt or respond to feedback	Aquino et al. 2024	Medication delivery device that administers a fixed dose, regardless of the patient's current condition
(on-market) Adaptive (sometimes referred to as self-learning systems)	Using on-market retraining methods to adapt to new data or experiences, which could be in a periodic (batch) process, or could be (as methodologies advance) continuous. Changing on-market performance over time based on feedback, training data, or real-world usage, dynamically adjusting AI-models and processes	Petersen et al. 2021	AI-powered diagnostic system that constantly changes its predictions by analysing new patient cases

4 Lifecycle approach to assessing DHTs

4.1 Rationale for a lifecycle approach

DHTs evolve through a series of stages from early concept to widespread use. A lifecycle approach to evaluation can ensure that the right questions are asked and answered at the right time, using appropriate methodologies. However, DHTs pose a challenge for life cycle-based evaluation because their heterogeneity means there are multiple lifecycles and evaluation requirements.

ASSESS DHT developed a life cycle evaluation approach based on the IDEAL framework (McCulloch, 2009; Hirst, 2019). At early stages in the lifecycle of a technology, emphasis is placed on technical performance and usability in simulated or controlled environments. As the DHT lifecycle progresses, evaluations focus on feasibility, human factors, and user trust. In later stages of the lifecycle, rigorous comparative studies and long-term surveillance take precedence.

The lifecycle evaluation approach supports HTDs to understand DHT evidence generation requirements. It also supports HTA assessors to understand whether a topic is suitable for HTA, where there may be gaps in the evidence generation and provides criteria that can support early HTA advice and processes.

4.2 Description of the lifecycle

The ASSESS-DHT framework is based on the IDEAL framework and identifies five major stages in the DHT life cycle: Preclinical, Experimental, Early Clinical, Comparative, and Surveillance:

- ▶ In the **Preclinical Stage**, DHTs are evaluated outside clinical settings for technical functionality, potential risks, usability and human factors, and regulatory safety requirements. For example, digital components are tested for accuracy, and their input/output systems are validated for reliability. Simulation and stress testing under laboratory conditions helps to identify and eliminate imperfections in design.
- ▶ The **Experimental Stage** involves the first live interaction of the DHT with patients in real clinical environments. The evaluation approach differs between the DHT functional categories which directly affect the patient or their treatment (prevention, disability alleviation, treatment recommendation and treatment conduct) and those which do not (monitoring, diagnosis, prognosis). The first group require initial carefully de-risked “First in Human” studies to assess safety and function, followed by a consecutive case series in which any iterative improvements based on experience are documented, explained and their effects evaluated. The second group can be safely evaluated using “Shadow mode” studies, where the DHT is fed patient data and produces an output e.g. a prognostic prediction, but this is not shared with the clinical care team or used in treatment.
- ▶ In the **Early Clinical Stage**, the DHT is evaluated in a larger, heterogeneous population of patients in multiple settings. No comparator is necessary, as the aim is to estimate effectiveness, not comparative effectiveness. Studies at this stage also assess subgroup variations in outcome, operator learning curves, user trust in AI tools, and the DHT’s effect on workflow and clinical processes.
- ▶ In the **Comparative Stage**, the technology is benchmarked against existing standards of care. Often, randomised controlled trials are used for therapeutic interventions, though other sources of comparative evidence may be used if applicable. Diagnostic and prognostic tools are commonly compared with “gold standard” methods using blinded, parallel evaluations of the same patient. Cost-effectiveness analyses are often integrated into this stage.
- ▶ Finally, the **Surveillance Stage** entails long-term, real-world monitoring using registries and real-world data (RWD) sources like electronic patient records. This stage detects late safety signals, tracks AI model drift, and evaluates sustained performance and clinical utility. For DHTs using

adaptive AI, regular revalidation and audit mechanisms are necessary to maintain trust and safety.

It is important throughout each stage of the lifecycle to critically assess the quality of evidence as this can impact the usability and reliability of results. For example, if key risks are not identified or usability not optimised in earlier stages, comparative trials may be compromised, leading to negative, flawed or uninterpretable results. The use of a life cycle model helps ensure that foundational data support the assumptions and methodologies of subsequent evaluations. It also enables regulatory and HTA processes to converge more effectively by creating a common language to describe the stage of evolution of the DHT and thereby facilitating shared use of data and avoiding redundant studies.

Different decision-makers, in general, prioritise different evidence types: Regulators focus on safety and performance, HTA bodies emphasise comparative and cost-effectiveness, and payers are concerned with budget impact and scalability. A comprehensive evidence strategy should take this into account, including multiple evidence types and, where necessary, demonstrating effectiveness and value in an efficient way through the lifecycle.

4.3 How the lifecycle is used

Five life cycle stages form the basis of the ASSESS-DHT matrix, which links each stage to corresponding evaluation recommendations. The figure below presents the ASSESS-DHT evaluation matrix, which illustrates how recommendations are mapped across intended purpose and stages.

Figure 3. Graphical representation of the ASSESS-DHT life-cycle stages.

The ASSESS-DHT stages are represented in yellow, and their respective main focuses of evaluation in green. The IDEAL stages are presented in red to illustrate the parallel with this Framework. Depending on the nature of the DHT, the first in human studies take place at various times.

The table below summarises the main questions which evaluation needs to address at each life cycle stage. This simplified overview serves as a guide for understanding where a technology fits in the broader evidence generation pathway:

Table 6. Evaluation Focus at Each Lifecycle Stage

Lifecycle Stage	Simplified Evaluation Focus
Preclinical	Is the technology safe and usable in lab or simulated settings?
Experimental / Local Validation	Can it work safely in a real clinical setting, and has it been developed to a stable optimised state?
Early Clinical	How does it perform in real use, including in specific sub-groups? Are there important user learning and trust issues to resolve? Can we achieve consensus on a trial protocol for a randomised controlled trial?
Comparative Study	Is it better or equivalent to current care? Is it effective and cost-effective?
Long-term Study	Does it remain safe and effective over time? Are there any rare problems or performance shifts?

Initially, HTA bodies must determine the correct life cycle stage of the DHT. This can be done through a structured classification process that begins with a rapid evidence review—examining available documentation such as technical reports, usability studies, clinical data, and regulatory submissions (Figure 4). Based on this review, the user can match the evidence against the stage definitions. For example, if a DHT has only been tested in a simulation environment with no clinical contact, it remains in the Preclinical stage; if it has been used in clinical care in multicentre studies but lacks comparative data, it would be considered Early Clinical. The user should also determine whether the requirements of earlier stages have been met before the DHT advanced to a more mature phase, or whether any of these have been omitted.

Figure 4. Flowchart to determine the study Stage in the ASSESS-DHT life cycle Framework

Once the appropriate stage is provisionally determined, the DHT is categorised into one of seven functional categories or purposes that identify technologies with the same life cycle: sensing/monitoring, diagnostic (for diagnosis), prognostic (for prognosis), prevention, disability alleviation (for disability support), treatment recommendation and treatment conduct (for treatment delivery). The functional categories are described below.

Table 7. Description of the functional categories

Functional Category	Brief description
Diagnostic	DHTs which use measurements of patient characteristics and information about the range of values in diseased and normal states to classify for the presence or likelihood of disease
Disability Alleviation	DHTs which restore or support functions lost or impaired through disease or infirmity
Prevention	DHTs which prevent disease or accidents or minimise risks of injury
Prognostic	DHTs which use measurements of patient characteristics to predict outcomes
Sensing & Monitoring	DHTs which record and monitor physiological signals
Treatment Delivery	DHTs which directly administer treatment following commands from a human operator or a computer
Treatment Recommendation	DHTs which recommend (the most appropriate) treatment options to healthcare professionals.

In addition to assigning the DHT to the relevant functional category, there are six cross-cutting “modifiers,” (level of risk, AI integration, autonomy, Human Factors, evidence and telemedicine) that give additional evaluation recommendations that affect safety and evidence requirements – a DHT may have one, several, or none of these modifiers. The modifiers are described in the table below.

Table 8. Description of the Modifiers

Modifier	Brief description
Artificial Intelligence	DHTs using artificial intelligence (AI) as an essential component of device function
Autonomy	DHTs able to conduct part or all of their function with a set degree of autonomy
Human Factors	DHTs interacting with human users (healthcare professionals or patients) in the conduct of their function
Interoperability	DHTs interacting with other networked or linked DHTs which may affect each other’s function in a healthcare system
Telemedicine	DHTs used remotely from their main control centre and necessitating the digital transfer of information between human users and their attending healthcare professionals.

Using the classification algorithm, users can consult the full matrix of evaluation recommendations to identify the evaluation recommendations specific to that DHT. This matrix includes both function-specific and modifier-based guidance and spans all five life cycle stages. The full matrix of ASSESS-DHT evaluation recommendations, organised by function, modifier, and lifecycle stage, is presented in Annex 1.

ASSESS-DHT has created an online tool which automates the provision of evaluation recommendations once the user enters the life cycle stage, functional categories and presence of modifiers - see Annex 2.

4.4 Resources

[ASSESS-DHT Lifecycle online tool](#)

4.5 References

McCulloch P, Altman DG, Campbell WB, Flum DR, Glasziou P, Marshall JC, et al. No surgical innovation without evaluation: the IDEAL recommendations. *Lancet*. 2009;374(9695):1105–12.

Hirst A, Philippou Y, Blazeby J, Campbell B, Campbell M, Feinberg J, et al. No Surgical Innovation Without Evaluation: Evolution and Further Development of the IDEAL Framework and Recommendations. *Ann Surg*. 2019 Feb;269(2):211–20.

Sedrakyan A, Campbell B, Merino JG, Kuntz R, Hirst A, McCulloch P. IDEAL-D: A rational framework for evaluating and regulating the use of medical devices. *BMJ*. 2016 Jun 9;353:i2372.

Vasey B, Nagendran M, Campbell B, Clifton DA, Collins GS, Denaxas S, et al. Reporting guideline for the early-stage clinical evaluation of decision support systems driven by artificial intelligence: DECIDE-AI. *Nat Med*. 2022;28(5):924–33.

5 Health problem and current use of the DHT

5.1 Overview of the domain

The “health problem and current use of the DHT” domain describes the target condition, target population, epidemiology and the availability and patterns of use of the technology in question. This domain aims to provide an understanding of how the technology will be used, by who and its place in current clinical management and is often described in HTA frameworks as “background information”.

This domain is important for the assessment of DHTs because HTA addresses a policy question that is embedded in the current management of a condition and the intended purpose of a health technology. Information in this domain is closely linked to scoping activity and is related to elements of the scope such as the population, intervention and comparators.

The HTA Core model (EUnetHTA, 2016) provides a comprehensive overview of questions covered in this domain and these can also be used to support the assessment of DHTs. The EU HTA regulation guidance on completing a submission for a JCA also provides guidance about how to provide an overview of the medical condition, characterise the target population and describe current clinical management much of which is also relevant for DHTs.

This manual chapter highlights a small number of elements in this domain for which there can be specific considerations when assessing DHTs (see table below).

Table 9. Topics and issues related to the health problem and use of the DHT

Topic	Issue	Link
Target population	Who is the target user of the DHT?	Target population
	What is the target condition for the DHT?	
Intended purpose	What is the intended use or purpose of the DHT?	Intended purpose
	What is the place of the DHT in the care pathway?	

5.2 Topic considerations

5.2.1 Target population

How is this topic relevant to the assessment of DHTs?

DHTs can have multiple and different possible uses, and the target population needs to be clearly defined at the start of the HTA process. An HTA may not cover all possible uses and the HTA process should check the alignment of the proposed use and target population with regulatory approvals. For further guidance, refer to 2.1 Scoping.

Table 10. Target population considerations

<i>Target Population</i>
<p>Considerations for all DHTs</p> <p>The following criteria apply to all DHTs regardless of the medical purpose, risk, or stage in the lifecycle:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Who is the intended user (e.g., service users, clinical staff)? ▶ Who should not be using the DHT? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Are any restrictions clear to potential purchasers and users?
<p>Additional considerations based on the taxonomy</p>

Purpose	None identified
Risk	Vulnerability of users / intended population
AI	None identified
Considerations based on lifecycle	
Evidence requirements	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Description of the condition or context in which the DHT is expected to be used ▶ Description of the characteristics of the population who are expected to use the DHT. ▶ Calculate the size of the target population using appropriate national or local sources (e.g., accurate epidemiological data of prevalence and incidence of the relevant health problem), or expert estimates if this is not available. 	

5.2.2 Intended purpose

How is this topic relevant to the assessment of DHTs?

DHTs may be purposively designed to be transdiagnostic or to target multiple conditions. They may also present several intended purposes in their technology descriptions which may or may not be reflected in the technology's design, regulatory approval, and evidence. The regulatory processes for a DHT differ depending on whether the DHT has a medical purpose and the risk classification of the DHT.

Table 11. Intended purpose of the DHT

Intended purpose	
Considerations for all DHTs	
The following criteria apply to all DHTs regardless of the medical purpose, risk, or stage in the lifecycle:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ What issues does the DHT claim to address? ▶ Is the DHT intended to be used to diagnose, treat or inform clinical management? ▶ Does the DHT replace or compliment standard care? ▶ Is the DHT used for self-management or under the support of a healthcare professional (e.g., self-management, blended care, facilitates interactions with healthcare professional, remote monitoring by healthcare professional)? ▶ Is the product already in use in the country of application or worldwide? Where, and for how long? What is the level of adoption? ▶ What is the current pathway or system processes for this condition? 	
Additional considerations based on the taxonomy	
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ For DHTs for behaviour change: ▶ Is the target behaviour clearly specified? Does the DHT assess capability to change?
Risk	None identified
AI	None identified
Considerations based on lifecycle	
Evidence requirements	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Describe the intended purpose of the DHT. ▶ Describe the existing care pathway or system processes for intended purpose and population. ▶ Describe how the existing care pathway will change with the introduction of the DHT. 	

5.3 Resources

ASSESS-DHT WP2 D2.2: Landscape and gap analysis of existing value frameworks and methods for the assessment of digital health technologies

5.4 References

Guidance on filling in the joint clinical assessment (JCA) dossier template – Medicinal products
[HTAR Guidance-on-filling-in-the-JCA-dossier-template](#)

EUnetHTA Joint Action 2, Work Package 8. HTA Core Model[®] version 3.0 (Pdf); 2016.

6 Description and technical characteristics of the DHT

6.1 Overview of the domain

The “Description and technical characteristics of the DHT” domain provides details about the DHT, including its functions, design and technical characteristics. This domain seeks to gather technical information that describes the DHT.

This domain includes three key topics covering 9 issues: product information, design and development and technical performance. These topics and issues are listed in the table below.

Table 12. Topics and issues related to the technical characteristics of the DHT

Topic	Issue	Link
Product information	General description of the DHT	Product information
	Functions of the DHT	
	Customisation	
Design and development	Appropriateness of the design and ease of use	Design and development
	Credibility and validity of the design and content	
	Target group involvement in design and development	
Technical performance	Technological and technical stability of the DHT	Technical performance
	Processes to ensure the reliable performance of the DHT	
	Feedback on technological issues and user experiences	

6.2 Product information

How is this topic relevant to the assessment of DHTs?

The assessment of DHTs requires clear understanding of the technology including its functionality and features. This is necessary to understand how the technology would be used in the care pathway, how it may compare to standard care, and the relative risks and benefits associated with its use. DHTs may have specific technical requirements for use, such as an active internet connection or dependence on additional devices. This may impact how, when, and by whom a DHT can be used, resulting in a need for this information to be clearly provided at the outset of an assessment.

Many DHTs are multifunctional by design which can impact how they are used within the health and care system. To fully assess the relative benefits and risks of using DHTs, assessors must gather sufficient information to clearly understand what the technology and its components do, how the technology description aligns with the claimed benefits and intended use, and which of these functionalities are regulated under the MDR. DHTs can include additional functions that fall outside of its medical purpose and regulatory approvals. The risks and benefits of any additional functionality needs to be considered by the assessor, including any options to customise the selection of features or modules in the DHT which could impact the intervention or delivery of care. Assessors should also consider how closely the description of the intervention presented in the technology’s description aligns with the use of the technology in clinical studies and in the real-world, as this could impact the DHT’s relative benefits and risks.

As DHTs undergo continuous updates and live development, this may result in a change of the functions, features, and effectiveness of these technologies over time. Assessors must determine the version of the DHT being assessed, the version of the DHT in the evidence and supporting documentation, and any

planned or anticipated updates to the technology including timelines for these updates. Assessors should consider the nature of any modifications across versions of the DHT, and how these revisions impact the applicability of evidence. This is particularly relevant to DHTs using adaptive AI components which could change continuously overtime to adapt to new data or experiences, as HTA agencies cannot pre-approve future versions of DHTs.

Table 13. Product information considerations

Product Information	
Considerations for all DHTs	
A detailed description of the technology is needed for all DHTs regardless of the medical purpose, risk, or stage in the lifecycle. This should include the following information:	
The name and version of the DHT, including unique device identifier and a detailed description of the DHT (if available)	
The key components of the DHT and how they interact	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ The input(s) (symptoms, patient-generated data, etc.) and output(s) (inform, treat, diagnose) of the DHT ▶ How the DHT will achieve the desired impact and the mechanism of action ▶ If the DHT uses an algorithm, the type used (e.g. AI, Boolean, etc.) ▶ The function(s) the DHT performs (e.g. data collection, assessment, monitoring, etc.) ▶ The features of the DHT (e.g. reminders, health warnings, advice, recording, etc.) ▶ Whether any health content is interpreted by the DHT or by a human, or a mixture of both 	
The connectivity that the DHT requires, such as internet or mobile data, and whether the DHT is still able to function offline.	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Any resources available online/offline for use of the DHT, and whether these are kept up to date 	
The hardware requirements of the DHT	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ The operating system(s) and platform(s) the DHT is available on ▶ The device(s) the DHT is compatible with 	
Whether the DHT is likely to increase awareness, knowledge, or understanding of a specific medical condition	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Whether the DHT is likely to change attitudes, increase intentions to change, or encourage further help seeking 	
The user’s experience of the DHT, including accessibility and navigation	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Whether users can update their data at any time, and the ease of doing so ▶ Whether notifications and alerts can be customised, and whether users can opt out of non-critical alerts (if applicable) ▶ The language(s) the DHT is available in 	
Additional considerations based on the taxonomy	
Purpose	For DHTs with multiple purposes, gather information on all functions and consider how these relate to the indication for use within the DHT’s CE marking (if applicable/available). For DHTs for treatment, include information on the mode of action of the device.
Risk	No specific considerations based on the requirement levels
AI	For DHTs with AI components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Does the DHT use static or adaptive AI components? ▶ The role of AI in the DHT (e.g., visualisation only, decision making, AI-assisted, AI-controlled) ▶ The role of the human using the technology in relation to the AI ▶ The tasks that are automated by the algorithm (e.g., supervised classification, defining classes, ranking, regression, segmentation, etc.) ▶ The type of model and learning used to develop the DHT. ▶ Whether the AI-based technology can be retrained for quality and accuracy.

- ▶ Any plans to update the model or training dataset.
 - ▶ Information on how this could impact the use and effectiveness of the DHT.
- For DHTs with adaptive AI components:
- ▶ Whether on-market retraining methods are periodic or continuous.
 - ▶ If periodic, how often the retraining is expected to occur.
 - ▶ The potential impact of retraining on the use and effectiveness of the DHT.

Considerations based on lifecycle

Based on the DHT's current lifecycle stage or product readiness level, consider:

- ▶ The updates and modifications that have been made to the DHT over time
 - ▶ Are these reflected in different versions or device identifiers
- ▶ How the technology is expected to change as it progresses through the lifecycle.

Evidence requirements

- ▶ Detailed description of the functions of the DHT, which can be supplemented by plans, diagrams and photos and information about the claims being made in the description or content. This should include information on the main functional elements of the technology, parameters detected by the device and type of data transmission used, components of the DHT, and whether users interact passively or actively with the technology. Potential sources of information include the technology website, instructions for use, technology manual, technical reports, HTA reports, published literature, clinical studies, app stores, the DHT itself, company submission checklist.

6.3 Design and development

How is this topic relevant to the assessment of DHTs?

The design and development of a DHT has significant impact on its acceptability to users, and in turn, its overall effectiveness and safety. Elements such as usability, ease of navigation and accessibility are crucial, particularly when the DHT is intended to be used by patients. Evidence of the DHT being developed in collaboration with the intended user group can help show that a DHT is more likely to be accepted by the intended user.

Table 14. Design and development considerations

Design and development

Considerations for all DHTs

The following criteria apply to all DHTs regardless of the medical purpose, risk, or stage in the lifecycle. Include the following information:

The design of the DHT

- ▶ The design of the DHT, and whether it is appropriate for its intended purpose.
- ▶ Design features, such as clarity of text, readability across platforms, changes to orientation (landscape/portrait)
- ▶ Whether the DHT is easy to navigate and use
- ▶ Any independent evaluation of the DHT's usability, and the results of that evaluation

The content of the DHT

- ▶ Whether the DHT uses content that is credible, relevant, robust and up to date.
- ▶ Whether the DHT presents this content in a way that is easy to understand for the user

User input

- ▶ The users that were involved in the design and development of the DHT, how they were involved, and how diverse the user input was
 - e.g., were people from a variety of populations involved?

- ▶ Whether health professionals were involved in the development of the DHT, and how they were involved.

The coding standard used in the development of the DHT, and whether this is secure and appropriately documented

- ▶ Is there a detailed software development process for the DHT, and does it cover the standards, methods and tools to be used?

Does the DHT have specific, measurable and achievable goals? Are these specified/obvious within the DHT?

Is regular feedback provided on the achievement of goals?

Additional considerations based on the taxonomy

Purpose	None identified
Risk	None identified
AI	The development process that was followed to prevent biases in therapeutic algorithms

Considerations based on lifecycle

Evidence requirements

- ▶ Design of the DHT including UI design, persuasive design, visual design (aesthetics i.e., the degree to which the DHT interface applies design elements, colours and fonts in a logical way; size; layout), readability, visual information, customisation, interactivity, format
- ▶ Date and source of content with documentation and copyright compliance. Source should point to current and accepted protocols and guidelines. Additionally, the content within the application should align and not deviate from the referenced source
- ▶ The DHT clearly indicates who reviewed the content and when the content was last updated. Any relevant conflict of interest of contributing authors must be disclosed
- ▶ If the DHT is based on content other than from a recognised source, documentation about how and when the content was formulated, including information regarding its relevancy and reliability
- ▶ Method or protocol for determining if DHT content requires updating, including annual review schedule
- ▶ Disclosures, as needed, to prevent deception and if DHT needs additional fees for full access. Such disclosures shall be presented in a clear and conspicuous manner
- ▶ Information about the development process including information about involvement of different user groups and experts in the development and design of the process and outcomes of this user engagement.
- ▶ Company's process of developing the therapeutic algorithm including mechanisms to prevent biases in therapeutic algorithms
- ▶ Company should show processes to maintain valid, accurate and comprehensive health information, including regular review and updates by experts
- ▶ DHT should have an easy-to-locate help section that consolidates all information intended to assist the user. Help features and informational links should be embedded in the DHT when users may be likely to need them

6.4 Technical performance

How is this topic relevant to the assessment of DHTs?

The technical performance of a DHT directly impacts its effectiveness and safety in a clinical setting. Unlike traditional health technologies, DHTs can update, re-version and change in functionality. In addition to standard consideration of a DHT's effectiveness, assessors should note the impact of post-deployment updates and changes to the DHT over time.

Table 15. Technical performance considerations**Technical performance****Considerations for all DHTs**

The following criteria apply to all DHTs regardless of the medical purpose, risk, or stage in the lifecycle:

The steps and plans that have been made to ensure:

- ▶ the reliable performance of the DHT
- ▶ that the DHT and its components work as expected in terms of technological and technical stability
- ▶ that the DHT creates accurate measurements and data
- ▶ that the DHT can deal with significant increase or spike in demand
- ▶ that the DHT is robust to user configuration in an unintended way

The release, deployment and maintenance of the DHT

- ▶ The release and deployment process
- ▶ The update schedule of the DHT, including strategy for updates and patches
 - Are users notified of all updates?
 - Are updates based on improved research and recommendations?
 - Are updates well documented - e.g. patch notes?
- ▶ The data collection, automatic fault and performance monitoring processes
- ▶ Any support available to the user of the DHT for feedback or error reporting
- ▶ Does the developer have a documented plan for decommissioning the product?

The information provided to the user (e.g., notifications, alerts)

- ▶ Whether error logs, notifications, alerts, etc. are stored within the app and easily accessible for future reference
- ▶ Does the DHT notify the user if it fails to connect to any peripheral or accessory devices?
- ▶ Is information stored in such a way that users can recover their data if they are disconnected at any point? (e.g., local cache)
 - When does this storage begin?
 - If users are disconnected during onboarding, are they able to recover previously entered data without need for re-entry?

Additional considerations based on the taxonomy

Purpose	Assessment of performance when compared to technical gold standard (e.g. manual blood pressure cuff reading) Product documentation showing the accuracy and reliability of any calculations as well as appropriate sources that support the validity of calculations, measures and other functions
Risk	None identified
AI	None identified

Considerations based on lifecycle**Evidence requirements**

- ▶ Description of how the DHT addresses maintenance
- ▶ Product notification, recovery and resolution plans
- ▶ Change management process for changes made to the DHT or critical systems
- ▶ Documented patch management process for systems and DHT
- ▶ Configuration management plan
- ▶ History of updates including details of software changes over time, e.g., whether adaptive changes (i.e. maintains software with dynamic environment), perfective (i.e. recoding to improve

performance), corrective (i.e. corrects problems), preventive (i.e. corrects latent faults before they cause operational problems)

- ▶ Assessment of Technical Stability
- ▶ Technical effectiveness or performance of DHT (reliability, validity, accuracy, sensitivity, feasibility)

7 Regulatory aspects

7.1 Overview of the domain

The “regulatory aspects” domain provides details about the regulation of DHTs and assessment of their compliance with relevant regulations at an EU level. This domain focusses on supporting HTA agencies to understand whether the technology has been through the relevant regulatory steps and has the appropriate certificates. Detailed advice on assessment is included under specialist topics.

Within a jurisdiction, different organisations have responsibility for the assessment of compliance. This chapter of the manual has an initial section designed to support HTA agencies to know what to request from an HTD to ensure that a DHT has the appropriate regulatory approvals. Specialist topics highlight areas where organisations within a jurisdiction (for example, HTA bodies, national regulatory authorities or another organisation with the designated responsibility) may be required or may wish to do further assessment at a national or local level depending on the healthcare system.

The regulatory landscape for DHTs is complex and DHTs may need to be compliant with multiple legislative documents including:

- ▶ Medical Devices Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2017/745): lays down rules concerning the placing on the market, making available on the market or putting into service of medical devices for human use and accessories for such devices in the Union.
- ▶ Artificial Intelligence Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689): lays down rules to promote the uptake of human-centric and trustworthy AI including: rules for placing on the market, putting into service and monitoring AI systems and AI models and prohibitions of certain AI practices.
- ▶ General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679): applies to the processing of personal data wholly or partly by automated means and to the processing other than by automated means of personal data which form part of a filing system or are intended to form part of a filing system
- ▶ European Health Data Space (Regulation (EU) 2025/327): establishes the European Health Data Space (EHDS) by providing for common rules, standards and infrastructures and a governance framework, with a view to facilitating access to electronic health data for the purposes of primary use of electronic health data and secondary use of those data.
- ▶ Cybersecurity Act (Regulation (EU) 2019/881): lays down a framework for the establishment of European cybersecurity certification schemes for the purpose of ensuring an adequate level of cybersecurity for Information and Communication Technology (ICT) products, ICT services and ICT processes in the Union.

Table 16. Topics and issues related to regulatory status

Topic	Issue	Link
Regulatory status	Does the DHT have the appropriate CE marks and certificates?	Regulatory status

7.2 Regulatory status

How is this topic relevant to the assessment of DHTs?

The regulatory requirements that will be required as part of the assessment process will depend on the DHT purpose, risk level and functions. When a DHT comes to HTA, the HTA agency needs to understand which preceding regulatory steps a DHT should have been through and what certification marks and documents a technology should have at point of assessment.

Table 17. Regulatory considerations

Regulatory status of the DHT	
Considerations for all DHTs	
This applies to all DHTs regardless of the medical purpose, risk, or stage in the lifecycle. The assessment should include the following information:	
Type of DHT:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Is the DHT regulated as a medical device? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If not, does the DHT have a medical purpose e.g. are there any concerns that it should be regulated as a medical device? 	
Regulatory classification of the DHT:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Whether the DHT complies with relevant medical device regulations, such as MDR/IVDR (CE marking), MHRA registration. ▶ Whether the DHT has CE/UKCA marking <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What is the risk class of the DHT? ○ Whether the DHT is regulated under MDD or MDR ▶ The indication(s) the DHT has CE/UKCA marking for ▶ Whether the DHT meets relevant safety requirements for medical devices (if applicable) ▶ Where compliance with relevant regional regulations is required, whether the necessary documentation has been prepared, and whether appropriately qualified personnel have been designated, in accordance with specified standards. 	
Additional considerations based on the taxonomy	
Purpose	For DHTs with multiple purposes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Which purposes has the DHT received CE/UKCA marking for? For DHTs that are not classified as SaMD or SiMD: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Why is the technology not considered a medical device?
Risk	
AI	For DHTs with AI components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Does the DHT comply with the AI Act?
Considerations based on lifecycle	
Based on the DHT's current lifecycle stage or product readiness level, consider:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Does the DHT require a CE/UKCA mark? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If yes, and the DHT does not yet have CE/UKCA marking, when is this expected? 	
Evidence requirements	
Information and certificates showing compliance with regulations and safety standards, including EU declaration of conformity or CE certificate from an appropriate notified body and other relevant safety and quality standards where applicable. CE/UKCA marking should be provided for the DHT and any accessories, where relevant. Supporting sources of information include instructions for use and technology manual, and may include the entirety of the DHT's technical documentation	

7.3 References

Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC [Regulation - 2017/745 - EN - Medical Device Regulation - EUR-Lex](#)

Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act) (Text with EEA relevance) [Regulation - EU - 2024/1689 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (Text with EEA relevance) [Regulation - 2016/679 - EN - gdpr - EUR-Lex](#)

Regulation (EU) 2025/327 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 February 2025 on the European Health Data Space and amending Directive 2011/24/EU and Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 (Text with EEA relevance) [Regulation - EU - 2025/327 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act) (Text with EEA relevance) [Regulation - 2019/881 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

8 Safety

8.1 Overview of the domain

In the EUnetHTA Core Model, safety is defined as an umbrella term for any unwanted or harmful effects caused by using a health technology. HTA should include the assessment of safety not only to ensure benefits for individual patients but also to inform policy makers. This principle equally applies to the evaluation of DHTs used by patients, families and healthcare professionals. Ensuring the safety of DHTs is essential to preventing unwanted harm, maintaining user trust, and supporting evidence-based decision-making in healthcare.

The EUnetHTA Core model provides a comprehensive overview of questions covered in this domain and these can also be used to support assessment of DHTs. Moreover, the EU HTA regulation guidance on completing a submission for a joint clinical assessment (currently only available for pharmaceuticals) also provides guidance about how to collect and synthesise the results regarding safety.

This manual chapter highlights elements in this domain for which there can be specific considerations when assessing DHTs. This domain includes three topics: clinical safety, technical safety and environmental and occupational safety. These topics and issues are listed in the table below.

Table 18. Topics and issues related to safety

Topic	Issue	Link
Clinical Safety	What are the potential harms and risks of using DHTs?	Clinical Safety
	Has the DHT undergone a risk assessment?	
	What safety and risk management measures does the company have in place?	
Technical Safety	What safeguards are in place to protect user privacy and safety?	Technical Safety
	How does the DHT ensure the accuracy and reliability of its information?	
Environmental and occupational Safety	What is the impact of the DHT on environmental and occupational aspects?	Environmental and occupational safety

The relationship between safety and the technical and regulatory domains often overlaps, as stated in the EUnetHTA Core Model. However, the safety domain is especially important in the assessment of DHTs. Ensuring that the DHT under assessment complies with national or regional regulations (e.g., obtaining CE marking, medical device regulation) is a critical aspect of safety assessment. Furthermore, the safety of a DHT is closely linked to its usability. Poor usability can lead to errors in data input or retrieval, as well as mistakes in communication and coordination processes, potentially compromising patient safety.

Moreover, the quality of data used in the algorithm development of a DHT, and in the case of AI-driven DHTs, the quality of the data used for AI training, are also significant factors affecting safety. Compliance with regulations, usability, and data quality are discussed in detail in the technical and regulatory domains and in the specialist topics.

8.2 Methods guidance

As stated in the EUnetHTA Core Model and the EU HTA Regulation guidance, it is essential to collect evidence from diverse sources to appropriately assess the clinical safety and technical safety of a DHT. Rather than relying on a single type of data, a comprehensive approach should be taken, integrating systematic literature searches and relevant documents provided by developers.

Literature Search

A literature review is a key method for gathering evidence. To ensure comprehensive coverage, multiple bibliographic databases (e.g., Medline, Embase) should be utilised, and searches should be as sensitive as possible. Additionally, since studies evaluating the effectiveness of a given DHT may be registered in clinical trial databases, it is recommended to search sources such as ClinicalTrials.gov and the EU Clinical Trials Register.

HTA Reports

HTA reports are also valuable sources of evidence. Reviewing how similar technologies have been assessed in the past, or whether the same technology has been assessed by another HTA agency, can provide useful insights for evaluating the safety of the DHT under assessment.

Other information sources

Once fully operational, European Database on Medical Devices (EUDAMED) can serve as an important resource for retrieving information related to Post-Market Surveillance and Vigilance. This allows for the identification of safety concerns discovered through post-market monitoring.

Documents Provided by Developers

Documents provided by the HTD can also serve as critical sources of evidence. These may include scientific publications, technical reports, and unpublished data. If the DHT falls under regulatory frameworks such as the Medical Device Regulation (MDR), regulatory documentation can also provide insights for HTA.

Additionally, documents related to technical aspects of the DHT, and risk management should be included. The following materials are particularly relevant:

- ▶ Product safety and technical specifications (linked to the technical description domain)
- ▶ Risk management plan (e.g., how to mitigate identified risks, emergency response process for users)
- ▶ User guidance provided by the developer, outlining how to safely operate the DHT

By systematically collecting and integrating these different types of evidence, the assessment of clinical and technical safety can be conducted with greater accuracy and reliability.

8.3 Topic considerations

8.3.1 Clinical Safety

How is this topic relevant to the assessment of DHTs?

Clinical safety is assessed by identifying potential harms, adverse events, and risks that may result from the use of DHTs by intended users—including patients, healthcare professionals, caregivers, and members of the public—and by evaluating the adequacy of measures to prevent and manage those harms, adverse events, and risks. In the EUnetHTA Core Model, "Patient safety" and "Safety risk management" correspond to what this manual defines as "Clinical safety." The evaluation of "Patient safety" and "Safety risk management" can be conducted using the EUnetHTA Core Model.

Unlike conventional medical technologies, however, DHTs can take various forms—ranging from treatment-support tools and home healthcare devices to remote monitoring and self-management applications used without direct supervision by healthcare professionals. Some DHTs also provide clinical or behavioural recommendations to users, including patients and healthcare providers, thereby influencing decision-making. Due to these characteristics, DHTs place greater responsibility on users' ability to understand and operate the technology appropriately, which increases the risk of errors,

misuse, and non-adherence. This in turn may compromise safety in real-world use, requiring considerations beyond traditional safety assessments.

Given these factors, the assessment of “Clinical safety” is essential to identify harms and risks that may arise from real-world use, implement mitigation measures, and ensure that DHTs contribute positively to healthcare without unintended harm

The scope of "clinical safety" includes the identification of potential harms, risk assessment, and risk management.

Table 19. Clinical safety considerations

Clinical Safety	
Considerations for all DHTs	
The following criteria apply to all DHTs regardless of the medical purpose, risk, or stage in the lifecycle:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Have any additional harm or adverse events on the user or the care/treatment they receive by using the DHT been adequately identified, assessed, addressed, and monitored? ▶ What is the risk class for the DHT? ▶ Are (potential) users of the DHT adequately informed about its health risks, contraindications, appropriate usage and limitations of use? ▶ Is the potential impact of the DHT on clinical decision-making assessed? ▶ Is the user required to obtain approval or guidance from a healthcare professional before using the DHT? ▶ Does the DHT provide users with emergency resources or facilitate provider communication, and are preventive measures in place to address known risks? ▶ Are the risk mitigation measures implemented by developers addressing patient, healthcare professional, and environmental aspects? ▶ How does the company collect, review, and act on safety concerns and incidents related to the DHT? ▶ What procedures does the company have in place to detect, report, and handle adverse events? 	
Additional considerations based on the taxonomy	
Purpose	None identified
Risk	An interventional DHT (e.g., drug-dosing calculator) carries higher risks and requires more detailed assessment compared to non-interventional wellness or lifestyle applications (e.g., activity tracker).
AI	None identified
Considerations based on lifecycle	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Risk analysis should be performed in the preclinical and experimental stages, with more detailed and rigorous data required for devices in the highest risk classes. ▶ Usability analysis is an important component of safety evaluation for DHTs, especially with reference to the human-machine interface. This analysis is appropriate at the preclinical and early clinical stages in most functional categories of DHT. ▶ Training and advice for users is closely allied to usability and should be evaluated at the same stage. Both should be based on empirical evidence or accepted guidelines ▶ Rare and delayed safety risks may not be adequately evaluated by RCTs or earlier types of clinical study. Is there data on clinical risk based on an appropriate type of large-scale population study e.g. a registry, or on relevant high-quality real-world datasets? ▶ DHTs based on adaptive AI, or which receive frequent software upgrades, will change their performance over time. Regular or continuous monitoring is therefore required for realistic evaluation. Is there a plan in place for this and when was it last updated? 	
Evidence requirements	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Provide relevant evidence regarding harm or adverse events (e.g., scientific articles). ▶ List any adverse events associated with the DHT that have been reported to a notified body, regulatory authority, or identified through other sources. ▶ Provide information on the risk classification of the DHT. ▶ Describe how users are adequately informed about the health risks, contraindications, appropriate usage, and limitations of the DHT. Provide details on the content, format, and delivery methods of this information. 	

- ▶ List the potential risks identified and specify when and how the DHT affects clinical decision-making.
- ▶ Provide details of the measures implemented to prevent the occurrence or recurrence of any reported events.
- ▶ Describe the emergency response process for users, including available resources and protocols.
- ▶ Specify under what circumstances the DHT requires approval from health professionals before use.

8.3.2 Technical Safety

How is this topic relevant to the assessment of DHTs?

Technical Safety is assessed by identifying and evaluating risks and undesirable consequences that may result from technical flaws, system design limitations, or inappropriate implementation of DHTs. These risks can affect intended users—including patients, healthcare professionals, caregivers, and the public—and may involve issues such as data inaccuracy, algorithmic bias, privacy breaches, security vulnerabilities, or system malfunction.

This topic focuses on evaluating risks from a technical perspective, which extends beyond the scope of the Safety domain in the EUnetHTA Core Model and reflects the unique characteristics and needs of DHT assessment. Some DHTs—particularly stand-alone applications—are designed for direct use by individuals without healthcare professional supervision. For example, many can be freely downloaded to personal smartphones, making them highly accessible but also increasing the risk of misuse or unintended consequences. This is especially critical for vulnerable users, such as minors or individuals with impaired decision-making capacity. Appropriate safeguards and consent processes must be in place to ensure their safe use.

Additionally, DHTs often collect and process sensitive health information. To minimise privacy risks and unintended collateral consequences, user data must be handled securely and in compliance with applicable regulations. Many DHTs also generate health-related recommendations, behaviour prompts, or data summaries. These outputs may indirectly affect clinical decision-making. While the clinical consequences of such decisions fall under the scope of Clinical Safety, the technical factors that lead to misinformation or bias—such as flawed algorithms, lack of transparency, or incomplete data—are within the scope of Technical Safety.

While detailed evaluations of technical aspects such as cybersecurity, AI model performance, and update mechanisms are covered under the TEC (Technology) domain and specialist topics, they are closely linked to safety. Therefore, evaluators must also consider how these technical aspects affect the DHT's overall safety, usability, and trustworthiness in real-world conditions.

The scope of Technical Safety includes the identification of technology-driven risks, their potential impact on users—particularly vulnerable populations—and the assessment of mitigation strategies implemented by developers.

Table 20. Technical safety considerations

Technical Safety (user protection, quality of information)

Considerations for all DHTs

The following criteria apply to all DHTs regardless of the medical purpose, risk, or stage in the lifecycle:

- ▶ Whether the intended user group of the DHT is a vulnerable population (e.g., minors or individuals with impaired decision-making capacity)
- ▶ What measures are in place to ensure the safety and consent process for vulnerable populations, or those requiring substituted consent? (e.g., user agreements, who has access to platform)
- ▶ How does the DHT evaluate and mitigate privacy risks and undesirable collateral consequences for all users?
- ▶ Is the information in the DHT evidence-based, accurate, and from reliable sources?
- ▶ How does the DHT mitigate risks related to biased or inaccurate information?

Additional considerations based on the taxonomy

Purpose	None identified
Risk	None identified
AI	Is there a strategy for managing the training data used for AI development?

Considerations based on lifecycle

- ▶ During the development phase of the DHT, have evidence-based strategies or guidelines been identified and incorporated into the design of any educational or training content? For example, a mental health application should align with established methodologies such as Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT). Similarly, educational content for patients with a specific medical condition should be based on appropriate clinical guidelines.

Evidence requirements

- ▶ Describe the safeguarding measures in place for communication or interaction within the DHT. Provide details on platform access control and safety measures, including protection for minors or individuals with impaired decision-making capacity.
- ▶ Specify the intended user group of the DHT, including whether it includes minors or individuals with impaired decision-making capacity. Describe measures to ensure their safety and the consent process (e.g., user agreements, access control).
- ▶ Provide information on protecting the privacy of users.
- ▶ Provide evidence demonstrating that the information in the DHT is evidence-based, accurate, and sourced from reliable references. Specify the sources of information, the methodology used to ensure accuracy, and any validation processes in place. If applicable, include details on expert review, peer-reviewed publications, or regulatory approvals supporting the credibility of the content.
- ▶ Provide information on potential sources of bias or inaccuracies in the clinical information used or generated by the DHT (e.g., incorrect data entry, data selection bias).

8.3.3 Environmental and occupational safety

In line with EUnetHTA Core Model, Environmental Safety and Occupational Safety should also be considered when evaluating the safety of DHTs.

The development and implementation of DHTs can be expected to have some level of environmental impact. This is also important when DHTs are used in conjunction with chemical substances or biological materials, as they may introduce unintended ecological concerns.

Similarly, Occupational Safety must be considered, ensuring that healthcare professionals and users are not exposed to risks such as ergonomic strain, prolonged radiation exposure, or other occupational hazards. A comprehensive evaluation of these factors is essential for the safe and responsible integration of DHTs into healthcare systems.

Although these aspects are not unique to DHTs, they remain relevant and can be appropriately assessed using the existing EUnetHTA Core Model framework.

8.4 Resources

ASSESS-DHT WP2 D2.2: Landscape and gap analysis of existing value frameworks and methods for the assessment of digital health technologies

8.5 References

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9 Clinical efficacy and effectiveness

9.1 Overview of the domain

The “clinical efficacy and effectiveness” domain covers the questions about whether a DHT can work under ideal conditions (efficacy) and whether the DHT works in practice (effectiveness). Efficacy is the extent to which a DHT does more good than harm, for example within the protocol of an RCT. Effectiveness assesses whether a DHT does more good than harm when provided under usual circumstances of healthcare practice. The focus of an HTA is the evaluation of the relative clinical effectiveness of the DHT compared to a relevant alternative intervention (e.g., treatment, diagnostic/prognostic test, procedure, etc) to determine the magnitude of health benefits and harms provided by the DHT.

This domain is important since in health policy, most actors, such as payers or decision-makers, primarily require information on the effectiveness and safety of a technology before other aspects, such as costs of a DHT, are considered. With the new EU HTA Regulation (EU-HTAR) being implemented since January 2025, a centralised procedure has been established to assess the relative clinical effectiveness and safety of health technologies¹. The regulation primarily includes medicinal products and certain high-risk medical devices and in vitro diagnostic medical devices. Other medical devices, such as DHTs that are not classified high-risk, may also be included in the joint work under voluntary cooperation in the future. Either way, much of the supporting material regarding processes and methodologies developed by the member states will be applicable to the effectiveness assessment of DHTs.

The “clinical efficacy and effectiveness” domain requires information from the “health problem and current use of the technology” domain, to specify the appropriate populations, interventions, comparisons and outcomes (PICO) for the scoping. There may also be an overlap with the safety domain. Information from the “clinical efficacy and effectiveness” domain is fed into the “costs and economic evaluation” domain to inform the assessment of cost-effectiveness.

The EUnetHTA Core model provides a comprehensive overview of questions covered in this domain and these can also be used to support assessment of DHTs. This manual chapter highlights several elements in this domain for which there can be specific considerations when assessing DHTs. This domain includes two topics, clinical impact and evidence base, which are listed in Table 21.

Table 21. Topics and issues related to clinical efficacy and effectiveness

Topic	Issue	Link
Clinical Impact	What is the medical focus of the DHT?	Clinical impact
	On what level does the DHT provide a clinical benefit?	
	Does the content or design of the DHT affect the clinical effectiveness of the DHT?	
Evidence Base	What type of evidence is required and what evidence is available?	Evidence base
	Has the DHT been properly validated?	

9.2 Methods guidance

The scope of assessing relative clinical effectiveness of a DHT should be defined by a set of parameters in terms of patient population, intervention, comparator(s) and health outcomes (PICO). The scope can

¹ The EU HTA Regulation has not yet been implemented for medical devices.

vary between different countries, depending, for example, on the standard of care that is used on a national or regional level. It can therefore be challenging to address PICO questions from all European countries by performing only one clinical study. In many cases, evidence synthesis is necessary where information from different sources is collected to generate the evidence needed to answer a certain PICO question. However, this requires the use of appropriate methods (e.g., pairwise meta-analysis, Bucher’s method, network meta-analysis, or matching-adjusted indirect comparison) to ensure that the different study populations are comparable and to adjust for differences in, for example, study design. RCTs with low risk of bias and an adequate sample size deliver gold-standard evidence, although this study design may not always be possible or feasible for DHTs. Non-randomised evidence, such as from observational studies, is usually associated with a higher risk of bias and degree of uncertainty of the evidence. It is important that appropriate methods are used to synthesise evidence from indirect comparisons when direct evidence from an RCT is not available to answer a PICO question.

The EUnetHTA Core Model states that different sources of information (e.g., databases, search strategies, manufacturers, clinical experts) should be consulted when performing an analysis of the clinical effectiveness of a health technology. The EUnetHTA Core model also describes what kind of information is required for the assessment, including the study type(s), design and outcome measures. Generally, the assessment may be based on the manufacturer’s submission file, a literature review (with meta-analysis if possible), and, if available, HTA reports published by other HTA bodies.

Guidelines developed and published under the EU-HTAR describe the process and requirements for joint assessment of clinical effectiveness of a health technology and may be used as additional guidance. A submission dossier template for the HTD as well as a clinical assessment report template for the assessors are annexed to the implementing regulation on joint clinical assessment of medical devices and IVD. A similar outline and standard could be useful for DHTs. Other useful guidelines regarding properly presenting evidence as well as how this evidence may be assessed can be found below:

- ▶ Methodological and Practical Guidelines for Quantitative Evidence Synthesis: Direct and Indirect Comparisons
- ▶ Guidance on outcomes for joint clinical assessments
- ▶ Guidance on the validity of clinical studies for joint clinical assessments
- ▶ Guidance on reporting requirements for multiplicity issues and subgroup, sensitivity and post hoc analyses in joint clinical assessments
- ▶ Guidance on filling in the joint clinical assessment (JCA) dossier template – Medicinal products

National frameworks, such as the NICE evidence standards framework for digital health and care technologies and the AQuAS methodological framework to carry out a comprehensive digital health technology assessment, may also provide valuable guidance to what level of evidence is needed to assess the clinical effectiveness of a DHT.

Certainty of the clinical evidence can be increased by presenting evidence from an RCT or other well-designed study with a direct comparison between the DHT and a relevant comparator where study limitations are clearly addressed. Alternatively, evidence from an adjusted indirect comparison by using appropriate methods, which are roughly described in the guidelines above, can increase certainty, and may affect a reimbursement decision or procurement strategy positively. Other factors will play a role too, such as costs, ethical or organisational considerations.

9.3 Topic considerations

9.3.1 Clinical impact

How is this topic relevant to the assessment of DHTs?

The overall aim of performing an HTA on DHTs is to evaluate their potential clinical impact on patients, the healthcare system and/or society based on relative clinical effectiveness between the DHT and the

current standard. The intended use and risk class of the DHT must be clearly specified since the medical purpose and risk determines the level of evidence required for assessing the clinical effectiveness of the product.

Clinical benefits, including health and behavioural outcomes, can be measured on different levels: an individual, organisational, and societal level. The relevance of each level is strongly dependent on national or regional regulations and settings which may affect the clinical impact of the DHT in a specific country. For example, whether a DHT is introduced on a national or regional level is reliant on whether there is an established structure for joint introduction, whether there is a reimbursement scheme for these types of technologies, national price negotiations, or only local procurements, who takes the decision on including the DHT in the national or regional healthcare system, as well as what the decision is based on (e.g., assessment of clinical effectiveness or health economic evaluation).

Other important factors that may affect the clinical effectiveness of a DHT include the content quality and the user-friendliness of the DHT. It is therefore important that the content of a DHT is accurate, comprehensive, consistent with current treatment guidelines, and within scope of the DHT's purpose. Similarly, the design must allow for easy and correct use or application of the DHT to ensure compliance by patients and consistency in, for example, treatment or diagnosis.

Table 22. Clinical impact considerations

Clinical Impact	
Considerations for all DHTs	
The following criteria apply to all DHTs regardless of the medical purpose, risk, or stage in the lifecycle:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ What clinical measures are used within the DHT? ▶ On what level does the DHT provide a clinical benefit: end user (personal level), organisation (improving care processes) or on societal/population level (decreased pressure on healthcare system, decreased costs for society, access to care)? ▶ Is the clinical benefit of the DHT relevant to the national procedure of implementing the DHT? ▶ What is the clinical (added) value: mortality, morbidity, quality of life? ▶ What is the organisational (added) value: deployment of healthcare personnel, or the reduction of (future) use of healthcare services and other medical devices or pharmaceuticals? ▶ What is the expected health impact compared with current care or system processes? ▶ What are the benefits of the DHT when used in practice? ▶ Does the DHT enhance patient engagement, improve access to care or adherence to therapy, or empower individuals to manage their health? ▶ Human factor analysis: how effectively is the technology used by patients and healthcare professionals in real-world settings? This goes beyond controlled trials and considers how the technology is actually used and the resulting benefits. 	
Additional considerations based on the taxonomy	
Purpose	The medical focus of the DHT determines the type of study that can be performed to generate evidence for the clinical efficacy of the DHT.
Risk	Do the clinical benefits outweigh any potential complications that may occur when using the DHT?
AI	Is the AI trained on an appropriate/relevant population?
Considerations based on lifecycle	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Change in design or content (i.e., an updated version of the DHT) may have implications for the clinical effectiveness of the DHT. Therefore, the assessment of one version may not be directly applicable to another version of the DHT. ▶ If the intended purpose and classification of the DHT changes, a new assessment should be done. 	
Evidence requirements	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Describe the health benefits and other outcomes (e.g., system efficiency, care outcomes, structural and procedural effects) associated with current practice and anticipated health benefits associated 	

with using the DHT. Sources of information should be from the most robust evidence available (e.g., randomised controlled studies, systematic reviews, real-world evidence, observational studies, expert opinion).

- ▶ To demonstrate benefits when used in practice, real-world evidence may show that DHT was acceptable to users, performed the intended purpose to expected level, was integrated into best practice, caused no unintended negative impacts, showed improvements in outcomes, and/or was used in line with expectations.
- ▶ For those DHTs where performance is expected to change over time (e.g., AI or machine-learning algorithms or expected updates), report post-deployment changes in performance (e.g., plans for updates, sources of retraining data, processes for measuring performance over time and detecting decreasing performance).

9.3.2 Evidence base

How is this topic relevant to the assessment of DHTs?

When performing an HTA of a DHT, it is essential that the provided evidence matches the intended use and claimed clinical benefits of the product.

To estimate the clinical effectiveness, care should be taken to choose the most appropriate comparator. The comparator is normally comprised of the existing clinical gold standard (standard of care) used to treat the condition that the intended use of the DHT is targeting. It should be noted that the relevant comparator may differ between different subpopulations within the same condition.

As described in 2.1 Scoping, evidence synthesis may be necessary to answer a certain PICO question if direct evidence from an RCT is not available. If so, appropriate methods must be used to synthesise evidence from indirect comparisons. This is to ensure a high degree of certainty and confidence in the presented evidence on which decision-making is based on. The evidence-based evaluation of the clinical effectiveness of a DHT within the HTA can contribute to improve equal implementation, use, and maintenance/support of the DHT, both from a geographical and a socioeconomic perspective.

Table 23. Evidence base considerations

Evidence Base	
Considerations for all DHTs	
The following criteria apply to all DHTs regardless of the medical purpose, risk, or stage in the lifecycle:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Is the level of the evidence available sufficient to establish intended use and clinical effectiveness of the DHT in the target patient population? ▶ Is the comparator comprised of the existing clinical gold standard in the same line of treatment of target population, i.e. standard of care? ▶ Are there any ongoing studies regarding clinical effectiveness? ▶ Are there implications for use outside of intended purpose (e.g., if innovation has been adapted or augmented beyond its original purpose)? ▶ Does the DHT use a validated model or recognised standard? ▶ What is the accuracy (constant error, e.g. closeness of the output to the true value)? ▶ What is the precision (variable error, e.g. reproducibility, consistency)? ▶ Has the DHT been clinically validated? 	
Additional considerations based on the taxonomy	
Purpose	Low risk DHTs will likely be associated with a lower level of evidence compared to high-risk DHTs, due to the regulatory requirements of high-risk medical devices
Risk	The type of evidence needed for an HTA is identified in the HTA scoping process. DHTs with high impact on patient or public health will likely be subject to a more rigorous evaluation, thus will the evidence requirements be higher than for low risk DHTs.
AI	Does the AI replace or support another method? There is a challenge to find or generate evidence on clinical effectiveness in short-term studies. Is the AI trained on or validated in the relevant population?

Considerations based on lifecycle

- ▶ Early stage DHTs have limited clinical evidence and may undergo several modifications during development.
- ▶ The clinical effectiveness of DHTs may be affected by implementation in the health care system and interaction with users, potentially changing their behaviour or working environment.
- ▶ DHTs could adapt and evolve as they are used, especially those with an adaptive AI component.
- ▶ Scientific studies for certification may lack information on comparative clinical effectiveness required for HTA.

Evidence requirements

- ▶ Documented evidence that sufficiently supports, describes, or establishes the intended use and claimed clinical benefits of the DHT.
- ▶ Describe the available evidence and its level of certainty, e.g., randomised controlled studies, systematic reviews, real-world evidence, observational studies, expert opinion.
- ▶ For those DHTs where performance is expected to change over time (e.g., AI or machine-learning algorithms or expected updates), post-deployment changes in performance (e.g., plans for updates, sources of retraining data, processes for measuring performance over time and detecting decreasing performance) must be reported.

9.4 References

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10 Costs and economic evaluation

10.1 Overview of the domain

This domain covers the aspects of costing and economic evaluation that present challenges for the assessment of DHTs. The economic impact of investing in DHTs is an essential component of HTA at local, regional and/or national level across EU countries.

Table 24. Topics and issues related to the costs and economic evaluation of the DHT

Topic	Recommendation made by EUnetHTA in Methods for health economic evaluations- a guideline based on current practices in Europe. May 2015
Type of analysis	<p>Which type of analysis is most appropriate for the DHT?</p> <p>Health economic evaluations may be conducted for all types of health care interventions. To enhance the usability of the economic evaluations, it is recommended that results be presented in terms of both a cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) and a cost-utility analysis (CUA). A cost minimisation analysis (CMA) is sufficient when it is demonstrated that there is no difference in effect between an intervention and its relevant comparators. If appropriate and adequately justified, a cost-consequence analysis (CCA) may be a useful alternative in cases where CEA and CUA cannot be undertaken.</p>
Study population	<p>Target population and subgroups. How is the study population described (age in range, demographics, socioeconomic, clinical characteristics etc.)?</p>
Setting and location	<p>What are the relevant contextual information of the DHT that may influence the findings?</p> <p>Provision of relevant contextual information that may influence the findings</p>
Intervention and Comparator	<p>Choice of comparator</p> <p>Does the comparator(s) against which costs and benefits are measured accurately reflect the decision problem?</p> <p>Provide a clear description of the intervention and the comparator and describe why those were chosen. What are competing alternatives?</p>
(Health)-related outcomes	<p>What are selected (Health)-related outcomes?</p> <p>Selection and measurement of outcomes</p>
(Health)-related outcomes	<p>What is an appropriate source of data for measurement?</p> <p>Source of data for measurement</p>
Resources and Costs	<p>How are resources and cost identified, measured and valued?</p> <p>Identification, measurement and valuation of resources and costs</p> <p>To facilitate adjustments of costs to local settings, it is recommended that the use of resources is clearly presented in natural units, e.g. hospital days or physician visits.</p>
Perspective	<p>Economic evaluations should at a minimum be conducted from a health care perspective. However, several countries require a societal perspective. Presenting the use of resources as related to other sectors of society may increase the usefulness of the analysis to more HTA bodies.</p> <p>Regardless of perspective taken, it is recommended that the use of resources is presented in as detailed a manner as possible. For example, if a societal perspective is used, indirect costs should be presented separately</p>
Time horizon	<p>What is the most appropriate timeframe for assessing costs and health outcomes?</p> <p>The primary time horizon for the reference case analysis should be sufficiently long to reflect all important relevant differences in costs or outcomes between the</p>

Topic	Recommendation made by EUnetHTA in Methods for health economic evaluations- a guideline based on current practices in Europe. May 2015
	technologies being compared. The choice concerning any alternative time horizon for the reference case analysis should be clearly justified and described._
Discount rate	<p>Rate(s) at which costs or health outcomes are discounted</p> <p>Most countries use a discount rate between 3 to 5 percent for both costs and effects. It is recommended that both costs and effects are discounted in the base case analysis with the same rate. Furthermore, sensitivity analyses that explore the effect of varying the discount rate and differential discount rates (that is a lower discount rate for benefits than costs) should be performed; setting both discount rates to zero is also recommended.</p>
Uncertainty	<p>Sensitivity analyses</p> <p>Uncertainty should be explored in sensitivity analyses. To meet the preferences of the majority of the countries, deterministic as well as probabilistic sensitivity analysis should be conducted at least for the main variables in the in the model.</p>
Use of models	<p>Choice of appropriate modelling technique</p> <p>The use of decision models is recommended. However, modelling should always be justified and be presented as transparently as possible so that it can be reproduced. The choice of appropriate modelling technique should depend on the research question. When data are extrapolated beyond the duration of the clinical trials informing the economic model, all assumptions need to be clearly presented and analysed using different scenarios. Providing an electronic version of the model to users could further enhance its transparency and usefulness.</p>
Presentation of results	<p>Presentation of costs, health outcomes, and incremental cost-effectiveness ratios (ICER)</p> <p>In a CEA or CUA, results should be presented in terms of absolute and incremental values, separately for both costs and health outcomes, and in terms of incremental cost effectiveness ratios (ICERs)._</p>

10.2 Methods guidance

EUnetHTA published in 2015 a guideline for methods for health economic evaluations based on current practices in (national) member state HTA agencies. This outlined current practice at that time for economic evaluation across member states, for all types of health technology. The recommendations are summarised in Table 25. For the purposes of this manual, these broad principles are taken as the foundation and starting point for an economic analysis. Therefore, they are not repeated in this manual.

DHTs raise other economic considerations, that can be grouped in the following categories. The issues overlap, and hence the categories are not mutually exclusive:

- The lifecycle of the technology
- The purpose and risk of the technology
- The nature of the decision that the HTA process will inform

10.2.1 Lifecycle

Figure 3 shows a simplified schematic of the lifecycle of a medicine and a device. Broadly, these phases correspond to “discovery”, “development”, “launch” and “post launch”. HTA for a given technology can in principle be undertaken at any point on the lifecycle, and even at multiple points, but the type of evidence available, and the nature of the decision that will be informed by this evidence, will be different at each point. Hence the economic evaluation will need to be appropriately adapted to these requirements.

Economic evaluation preceding the “development” stage

There may be circumstances when a HTA body may wish to conduct an economic evaluation at an early stage. For example, as part of early dialogue or commercial negotiation with a DHT developer, or because a government agency is working with a developer for the implementation of a custom-made DHT solution.

If HTA is undertaken during an early phase of development, the technology will be a concept or prototype. Evidence will be very limited in detail and scope, perhaps covering aspects such as the clinical needs of the target population, current treatment options at this time, technical performance of the technology, and investors' expectations about future pricing, revenue streams, costs and return on investment.

The economic evaluation may be used at this time to inform a decision whether to continue or not with public investment in the development of the technology or continue with further research. “Headroom analysis” may be a useful approach to explore the parameters that might be most influential or need more evidence (Sculpher et al., 1997).

Economic evaluation preceding the “launch” stage

Before they can be marketed for patients in the EU, health technologies must be certified by a competent regulatory authority (such as a notified body). For certification, the developer must present evidence that proves quality, safety and performance. Scientific studies may have been designed to meet the requirements for certification, with a different focus from the comparative clinical effectiveness that would typically inform joint EU HTA work (or national HTA where a JCA is not performed) and economic outcomes required at national level for HTA (Aranda et al., 2024).

HTA of DHT may be different from other technologies. DHT may undergo several modifications during the development stage, unlike medicines whose technical specifications (active ingredients, manufacturing quality, mode of administration etc) are usually fixed at the end of preclinical development. The efficacy and effectiveness of DHT could also depend on how they are implemented in the health system, and how they interact with users (including health professionals, patients and possibly back-office staff such as administrators) potentially changing their behaviour or working environment. Potentially, DHT themselves could adapt and evolve as they are used, especially those with an adaptive AI component (see “Purpose of the technology”).

These considerations suggest that methods for HTA and economic evaluation of DHT will need to be sensitive to the nature of evidence at the time of launch, the potential for learning and adaptation, and the need to consider multiple scenarios. It also suggests that HTA may be warranted post-launch to review relative clinical and cost-effectiveness and of the technology as used in practice (Kirwin et al., 2022).

Economic evaluation post-launch

The adaptive nature of DHT and the possible lack of RCT or other relevant evidence at launch may mean that health service decision makers may wish to conduct HTA and economic evaluation post-launch (Kirwin et al., 2022). Post-launch evidence could be informed by data generated in a formal post-marketing evidence study sponsored by the developer at the request of the regulator or HTA agency, and/or by RWD generated by the health service, or data generated by the DHT itself (see section 9.3.2 for more detail on evidence requirements where no RCT is available). The design of the economic evaluation at this point will depend to some extent on the decision that is going to be made (see section “Nature of the decision that the HTA process will inform”).

10.2.2 The purpose and risk of the DHT

The purpose of the DHT, the risk or vulnerability of the patients, and whether it includes an AI component will influence the evidence that is available at the time of the assessment, and the type of

decision that will be taken, and hence will influence the type of HTA and economic evaluation that should inform that decision.

Operational purpose DHT

DHT with an “operational purpose” might include back-office functions, patient management systems and so on. These refer to systems that are mainly used by healthcare professionals and administrative staff and not employed directly in individual patient care. Hence it may not be feasible or informative to conduct an economic evaluation that estimates clinical outcomes or Quality Adjusted Life Years (QALYs) in these circumstances.

A more relevant type of economic analysis to support decisions on investment or procurement of these systems might be a budget impact analysis, or a return on investment model (Banke-Thomas et al., 2015; Cordes, 2017). Decision makers should be aware of optimism bias. Uncertainty could be considered using scenario analysis.

Health and wellness DHT

This category includes DHT that inform and guide “well” individuals about healthy lifestyle choices. Outcomes depend on the user’s degree of engagement with the app and the extent to which behaviour is changed. The user may incur personal expenses or personal savings, depending on the type of app. These may include subscription fees for the use of the app, or expenses related with recommendations by the app, such as purchase of healthy foods, gym membership, and so on. There may also be personal savings to the user, such as giving up smoking etc. There may be non-monetary costs, such as the app making use of the user’s personal data, or the app delivering advertising.

Because there is not a direct “medical purpose” to these types of DHT, some countries may not reimburse them within the health system coverage. Nevertheless, other countries might consider reimbursement or part-reimbursement with co-payment. HTA agencies may wish to undertake HTA and economic evaluation in these circumstances. If there are benefits and costs falling on private users, as well as the requirement for personal engagement, a “healthcare service perspective” is unlikely to satisfactorily capture these outcomes. This suggests that economic evaluation could be engaged with a wider perspective that values outcomes to both health systems and private individuals. Decision makers might consider a cost-consequence analysis (Gomes et al., 2022), an extended CEA (Vallejo-Torres, 2023), a cost-benefit analysis (Pérez-Troncoso et al., 2021) or a multistakeholder value analysis (Charle-Maachi et al., 2022).

Medical purpose DHT – Prevention, monitoring, prognosis, diagnosis, treatment

The ASSESS-DHT taxonomy for DHT with a “medical purpose” (prevention, monitoring, prognosis, diagnosis, treatment) categorises DHT into four “requirement levels” according to the expected impact on patient or public health (low impact, medium, high or very high).

DHT with low impact (low risk and informing clinical management) may not be required to undergo HTA in some countries. In any event, low risk medical devices are subject to less stringent regulatory requirements, and this will mean that developers will not undergo the clinical studies required of higher risk technologies. It may not be feasible or informative to estimate final outcomes such as survival or QALYs for economic evaluation in low-impact DHT. A budget impact analysis may be considered sufficient by decision makers.

DHTs aimed at patients at higher risk and/or that drive or make clinical decisions are more likely to be selected for HTA and economic evaluation. In these situations, the scoping stage of the HTA process will need to identify the type of economic evaluation that is appropriate. DHTs with high impact on patient or public health will likely be subject to more stringent and rigorous regulatory and HTA evaluation. In these circumstances the EUnetHTA recommendations for the design of the economic evaluation may be applied.

10.2.3 The role of economic evaluation in the decision-making process

HTA is a normative process that informs a particular decision, in a specific context and time. The type of decision to be made will be influenced by the point in the lifecycle, and the expected impact on patient and public health, as discussed in the previous sections.

The following considerations may be important for decision makers evaluating DHT and may influence the design of the economic evaluation.

The type of financial package that will reimburse the DHT provider

The reimbursement package for a DHT may be considerably more complex than the conventional “price per unit” associated with medicines or devices. There may be fixed and variable cost components. The variable cost may be stepped according to the number of users or depend on the complexity of the interaction with the user. The reimbursement model may be subscription, per capita, cost-plus, etc. or permutations of these. The health service (or other government agency) may itself be an active partner in a consortium of developers.

The long-term financial solvency of the provider.

If the implementation and employment of a DHT requires a long-term commitment for all parties, it is in the interests of the health service “customer” that the reimbursement package is financially sustainable for all parties. Therefore, the financial security, risk and solvency of the counterparties may need be considered as due diligence.

Assessment of the supply chain.

The health service customer may need to be aware of which other suppliers are providing services under contract with the DHT provider (e.g. cloud computing, servers, AI, etc), to consider the viability, solvency and risk associated with this configuration.

The diversity of the DHT provider’s customer portfolio.

A provider whose only product is the specific DHT or whose only customer is the health service may be exposed to different financial risks compared with a provider with a diverse portfolio. This may mean that the HTA agency should assess the financial risks of the DHT contract both to the health service and to the solvency of the DHT provider.

The scalability of the DHT

A DHT may be developed and tested on a small scale, with the intention of rolling it out over a larger population over time. An assessment should be made as to whether evidence generated on a small-scale pilot is generalisable to a larger population.

Costs of entry and exit of the agreement

What are the implementation costs and who will incur them? To what extent is the implementation of the DHT reversible? Who has responsibility and bears the cost of collection, reuse, recycling or disposal of electronic waste? Who has responsibility and cost of compliance with data protection regulations and best practice over the lifetime of the DHT, including archiving data of patients who withdraw from the DHT program or die?

Post-launch evidence generation

What is the proposal for post-launch evidence generation, and who will incur the responsibility and the costs of delivery?

10.2.4 The perspective of the economic evaluation, including environmental impacts

A DHT may have attributes that extend beyond a health service perspective for economic evaluation (health service costs and health outcomes) that might be relevant in economic evaluation done under a broader societal perspective. The use of energy in AI is a controversial and evolving question. At the time of writing (spring 2025) AI uses considerable quantities of energy, and the amount of energy required depends on the complexity of the application and the amount of data that it is processing. This may mean that marginal costs increase with scale. However, the field is evolving rapidly (International Energy Agency, 2024). HTA agencies may consider EU and other policy on carbon pricing (Bobini & Cicchetti, 2024 ; MÉTHODOLOGIE D'ÉVALUATION DE L'EMPREINTE CARBONE DES MÉDICAMENTS, n.d.) . Options and consequences for measuring the environmental impact of health technologies and how to integrate it in economic evaluation and HTA have been reviewed in the EU funded HI-PRIX project.

Countries and pan-national bodies such as the EU are concerned about other relevant environmental impacts, including those associated with the development and manufacture of electronic products, and the imperative for a circular economy that prioritises reuse over recycling over disposal of electronic waste (A New Circular Economy Action Plan for a Cleaner and More Competitive Europe, 2020).

Some types of DHT require engagement with users or professionals, either in financial or non-financial ways. For example, DHT apps that inform decisions require patients or professionals to change their behaviour. In these cases, important outcomes and opportunity costs may be outside the health service perspective.

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11 Specialist topics

11.1 Data protection and privacy

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) defines a unified standard for data protection and privacy within the EU. This means that data protection and privacy principles should be integrated throughout the DHT lifecycle. Despite the implementation of the GDPR, inconsistencies in evaluation remain due to variations in national regulations and institutional focuses.

ASSESS-DHT have created criteria for data protection and regulatory compliance for health data used in DHTs, including AI. The criteria developed are categorised by taxonomy, lifecycle, and stakeholder involvement, and priority levels are assigned based on risk. This includes incorporating privacy by design and by default, conducting Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs), ensuring transparency and consent during data collection, and implementing robust security measures during data storage and processing. The role of taxonomy in shaping data protection requirements for digital health tools is also explored, highlighting the need to categorise requirements based on the type of DHT.

The document "Data Protection and Regulatory Compliance Criteria for Health Data Used to Develop, Validate, Deploy, and Use Digital Health Technologies (DHT) Including AI" outlines a comprehensive framework for ensuring data protection and regulatory compliance in digital health technologies. This framework aligns with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the AI Act, and the Medical Device Regulation (MDR), among other standards. An abridged version of the checklist based on mandatory elements is included in Annex 3.

11.2 Data quality

High-quality data is vital to the reliability and validity of HTA conclusions and clear data quality standards ensure that DHT assessments are both reliable and broadly applicable. A failure in data quality at any stage – input, processing, or output – compromises not only the DHT's performance but also patient safety and healthcare outcomes. This is more relevant when DHTs are incorporating AI algorithms within their technologies. AI algorithms are highly dependent on the quality and diversity of their training data to deliver correct, fair, and robust outcomes.

Interoperability and compliance with the European Health Data Space (EHDS) are also tightly linked with data quality requirements to support DHT integration into health systems, technologies need to securely and effectively interact with existing health information systems.

To help assessors and developers consider data quality of DHTs, ASSESS presents a data quality framework. The framework includes assessment criteria for data quality management and data quality dimensions for 9 core dimensions of data quality (see figure below). A separate checklist is available with data quality criteria towards the use of AI in Annex 6.

Figure 5. ASSESS-DHT data quality dimensions

The framework highlights the key aspects developers must address to ensure datasets are fit for purpose. While all dimensions are important, their relevance may vary depending on the specific goals and applications of a project. Assessors should therefore consider which issues are relevant and how to incorporate these in their assessment. The full framework and criteria are presented in Deliverable 3.2. to provide guidance for developers implementing data quality processes. A short version of the data quality checklist focussing on the data quality management and the dimensions of data quality is included in Annex 4 and 5.

11.3 Cybersecurity

A fundamental requirement of any medical device is its safe and secure functioning. While traditional medical devices mostly require occasional checks for mechanical or physical functionality, DHTs introduce new complexities. These go beyond hardware functionality and include cybersecurity aspects related to safe device control and task implementation, and secure system integration.

The EU Cybersecurity Act (Art. 2) defines cybersecurity as “all activities necessary to protect network and information systems, their users, and affected persons from cyber threats”, that is “any circumstance or event that could negatively impact these systems or their users”. Healthcare institutions are particularly vulnerable to cybersecurity threats due to their large operating scale, diverse device interactions, varying security levels, and involvement of multiple personnel which all contribute to the risks. The rapid digitisation of healthcare and expanded use of DHTs makes protection more critical and difficult as it introduces new security risks, but the benefits of efficiency and improved patient care make this adoption inevitable. Therefore, ensuring safe, secure systems at every level is essential, as in some cases, a single device vulnerability can compromise an entire network. Most critically, a compromised system can pose a tangible threat to patient safety.

The EU MDR applies as a comprehensive regulatory framework that governs the production, distribution, and safety of medical devices within the EU. This includes basic cybersecurity requirements to be followed by medical device developers. The rapid rise of digitisation in all industries has also led to additional legislations, such as the NIS directive and EU Cybersecurity Act (2019) which, though not DHT-specific, has implications for them. HTA bodies may also have their own national requirements to be met for devices to be suitable for reimbursement.

Various cybersecurity best practices and standards exist, which though valuable in their own regard also adds to the chaos of which of the differing requirements developers and HTA agencies must choose to follow. In HTA, the approach to evaluating cybersecurity varies depending on the member state. Due to differing national procedures, cybersecurity compliance is not routinely considered as part of the HTA process and is instead considered by the regulatory bodies. Some HTA agencies also request additional proof of compliance with cybersecurity guidelines and standards during their evaluation process. In these countries, cybersecurity certification is required from national agencies before reimbursement assessments proceed. Currently, while some individual member states use different cybersecurity certification schemes for medical devices, others do not have the same requirements leading to inconsistencies across the EU and duplication of effort between different agencies.

To address the challenges of fragmentation in cybersecurity standards and requirements across the EU, the ASSESS-DHT manual presents a high-level cybersecurity assessment checklist which was developed by TUD-EKFZ as part of WP3 Deliverable 3.3: Common EU checklist for cybersecurity of digital medical devices/When evaluating DHTs, assessors should consider whether:

- ▶ Additional verification of cybersecurity compliance beyond CE-marking is needed
- ▶ There is national cybersecurity certification available showing proof of compliance with cybersecurity guidelines and standards, such as ANS certification in France, BSI certification in Germany, and NHS DTAC compliance and Cyber essentials certification in the UK.

The full cybersecurity checklist including advice for developers on achieving the outlined criteria is provided in Annex 7.

11.4 Artificial Intelligence (AI)

The ASSESS-DHT taxonomy and lifecycle evaluation defines the different forms of AI and their associated considerations in HTA. In addition, ASSESS-DHT has created three further AI-specific checklists that can support specific aspects of evaluation.

11.4.1 Validation of AI-based decision support systems

This section presents a structured framework for conducting pre-deployment localised external validation using real-world data (PLV-RWD) of AI-based clinical decision support systems (AI-CDSS). Developed through a Delphi process with international experts, it provides practical guidance for both model creators and validators to ensure models are safe, fair, and clinically relevant before deployment.

Figure 6. Validation phase in the AI lifecycle.

The framework is organised into three blocks:

- ▶ **Block 1 – Pre-validation requirements:** Outlines essential information about the training and validation datasets, bias mitigation strategies, interoperability, and documentation standards needed before initiating external validation.
- ▶ **Block 2 – Operational validation process:** Provides guidance on selecting appropriate performance metrics, defining validation frequency based on model risk, assessing fairness and bias during validation, and applying explainability and interpretability methods.

- ▶ **Block 3 – Post-validation best practices:** Recommends strategies for responsible deployment, including bias governance, fairness reporting, regulatory alignment, user training, and continuous monitoring of model impact and sustainability.

This manual aims to support trustworthy, transparent, and adaptive AI validation practices in real-world healthcare settings.

11.4.2 Approaches for adaptive AI technologies in regulation, HTA and reimbursement

Draft guidance that aims to address the regulatory and HTA challenges associated with adaptive AI in healthcare. It has been formulated by integrating existing recommendations from the UK and internationally, along with insights from our other research. This document provides HTA assessors and developers of adaptive AI technologies with a framework to evaluate and manage the evolving nature of these systems. Ultimately, it seeks to ensure safety, effectiveness, and compliance while fostering innovation within the healthcare landscape.

11.4.3 Data quality criteria towards the use of AI

A checklist that outlines the data quality requirements for AI-driven DHTs. Developers must define and document the data quality standards tailored to the specific needs of their AI algorithms, addressing the unique challenges posed by these technologies. See Annex 6.

11.5 Human Factors

Information will be added in the final manual when associated deliverable is complete.

11.6 Information management

How is this topic relevant to the assessment of DHTs?

Compared to standard health technologies, DHTs may collect and rely on a large amount of data for core functionality, some of which may be sensitive in nature and thus is associated with privacy risks. Assessors should consider what data is collected by the DHT and whether it is relevant to the functionality of the DHT, as well as how data is protected and maintained. For more detailed assessment criteria, refer to Annex 4 and 5.

Table 25. Information management considerations

Information management

Considerations for all DHTs

The following criteria apply to all DHTs regardless of the medical purpose, risk, or stage in the lifecycle:

- ▶ User generated data
 - ▶ What user-generated data is collected by the DHT?
 - What is the source of this data? (e.g. questionnaire responses)
 - Consider whether this is sensitive information
 - ▶ What data does the DHT need from the user?
- ▶ Data storage and protection
 - ▶ Are data maintained locally (on-device) or online?
 - If locally, is it possible to create back-ups?
 - If online, is this in secure cloud storage?
 - ▶ Is there a clear and accessible data retention policy for the DHT?

Additional considerations based on the taxonomy	
Purpose	
Risk	
AI	
Considerations based on lifecycle	
Evidence requirements	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Organisation should have a process for tracking information and physical assets. ▶ Information assets should be classified based upon value to the organisations and outside regulations, e.g. public, internal confidential, sensitive ▶ Information from company on datasets used for training and validating DHT (including size, how data was labelled and ground-truth established, why and how datasets were collected, diversity, synthetic data) 	

11.7 Interoperability

How is this topic relevant to the assessment of DHTs?

The interoperability of a DHT directly impacts its effectiveness and the ability to implement the technology in practice. Similarly, depending on the data that is held and transmitted, assessors should consider any associated risk and safeguarding needed. For further information, refer to 11.3 Cybersecurity and 11.6 Information management.

Table 26. Interoperability considerations

<i>Interoperability</i>	
Considerations for all DHTs	
The following criteria apply to all DHTs regardless of the medical purpose, risk, or stage in the lifecycle:	
The data shared by the DHT	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Any other apps, networks and medical record systems the DHT shares data with ▶ Whether the DHT synchronises user preferences and information across devices ▶ The user’s ability to export data from the DHT, and the format of that data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Whether this is a commonly used, standard format 	
Data exchange	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Does the DHT use open standards allowing it to exchange data with other health apps or tools? ▶ The patient data that is saved, sent to or received from each specified system the DHT integrates with ▶ The user’s ability to transport data from the DHT to another interface 	
Does the DHT work within its user’s workflow?	
Additional considerations based on the taxonomy	
Purpose	
Risk	
AI	
Considerations based on lifecycle	

Evidence requirements

- ▶ The PHR systems with which the app connects (e.g. Microsoft HealthVault, Blue Button etc.) are specifically enumerated and documentation of the interoperability with each specified PHR is provided.
- ▶ Testing of interoperability features
- ▶ Technical Assessment Interoperability

11.8 Resources

ASSESS-DHT WP2 D2.2: Landscape and gap analysis of existing value frameworks and methods for the assessment of digital health technologies

ASSESS-DHT WP3 D3.1 Data Protection and Regulatory Compliance

ASSESS-DHT WP3 D3.2 Data quality assessment

ASSESS-DHT WP3 D3.3 EU checklist cybersecurity

11.9 References

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ANNEX 1: Full ASSESS-DHT Lifecycle Evaluation Matrix

Stage	Category	Function	Recommendation
Pre-Clinical	Function	All DHT - General	Is there a complete and precise description of the device with its technical specifications, which would allow the replication of the first tests in laboratory conditions?
Pre-Clinical	Function	All DHT - General	Has a software development lifecycle that is compliant with standard practices been completed for Software as Medical Device?
Pre-Clinical	Function	All DHT - General	Has a data management plan been put in place to increase data security and prevent the risk of data breach or loss?
Pre-Clinical	Function	All DHT - General	Has a comprehensive risk assessment been conducted addressing device-specific, user-related, and data-related risks, including safety, reliability, digital inclusion, and ethical considerations, with clearly defined mitigation strategies tailored to the intended use and target population?
Pre-Clinical	Function	All DHT - General	Has the developer provided evidence that the device fulfils its intended technical functions reliably and accurately, under expected conditions and across relevant scenarios, including compliance with applicable standards and performance expectations specific to its technological and functional design
Pre-Clinical	Function	Data Selection and Reporting	Has technical performance, including accuracy of data extraction and summarisation, processing speed, reliability, and robustness to variations in data quality, been verified?
Pre-Clinical	Function	Data Selection and Reporting	Has the developer submitted thorough risk assessments covering potential inaccuracies in data selection or reporting, misinterpretation of summaries, security breaches, data privacy violations, algorithmic bias, and software development lifecycle considerations?
Pre-Clinical	Function	Diagnostic	Has the predictive value of the device to discriminate between diseased and normal states in the light of contemporary pre-existing clinical data been demonstrated?
Pre-Clinical	Function	Diagnostic	Can the device produce consistent results in laboratory conditions with highly selected participants?
Pre-Clinical	Function	Diagnostic	Is there evidence to show the robustness of the device against environmental and biological influences and its ability to maintain and produce accurate measurement?
Pre-Clinical	Function	Diagnostic	Were the potential risks and benefits and the safety associated with the new device, or the new uses of an already existing devices assessed?
Pre-Clinical	Function	Disability Alleviation	Has the developer demonstrated compliance with applicable ethical standards or guidelines relevant to the target population?
Pre-Clinical	Function	Prognostic	Has the developer provided preclinical evaluation of the prognostic model's explainability and transparency?
Pre-Clinical	Function	Treatment Recommendation	Have ethical risks (e.g., bias in recommendations, transparency, responsibility) been identified and addressed in the preclinical assessment?
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Was the <i>in silico</i> DHT performance assessed? Do the results support the DHT intended purpose? How do these results stand to current standard of care?
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Were any differences in <i>in silico</i> performance for pre-specified subgroups and subgroups prone to performance biases identified?
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Are the quality of the training sets adequately described in terms of: acquisition process, representativity of the general and target population, missing data, representativity of expected data in clinical settings?
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Does the training and validation methodology hold to the current standards in terms of development and testing?
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Were any ethics methodologies used by the developers to compensate for existing biases? Are these methodologies likely to achieve their goals?
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Was adversarial testing conducted? Is the AI system robust to adversarial or aberrant input data?
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Autonomy	Has the developer conducted a commercial viability assessment including deployment cost, infrastructure needs, and compatibility with healthcare delivery models?
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Human Factors	Were potential users and other stakeholders (innovators, clinicians, caregivers,) consulted or involved in co-design of the DHT?

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Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Human Factors	Has the developer conducted a structured human factors evaluation involving intended users or their representatives, assessing usability, interface design, and user interaction through recognised methods, and has an iterative improvement process been employed based on early feedback
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Human Factors	Was a participatory design framework used with the future users or appropriate proxies or personas?
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Human Factors	Has a heuristic analysis using standard ergonomic principles been performed to assess the usability and the User Interface design?
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Human Factors	Have high-risk devices or those involving more complex tasks been tested in high-fidelity simulators such as a full-scale, simulated operating room with manikin.
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Interoperability	Has the data flow between the DHT and other clinical systems been modelled? Are interoperability requirements defined and documented?
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Telemedicine	How robust is the DHT against network disruptions? Has this been evaluated?
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Telemedicine	Have training programmes been developed for healthcare professionals and, where necessary, patient users? Are the training programs both addressing the correct use of the DHT and improving patients' health literacy for them to better understand their pathology and resources available from other accessible sources?
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Telemedicine	Is there evidence of a systematic usability assessment employing a recognised methodology to address the issues facing all system users? Is a process of iterative assessment and modification presented to show how the current model evolved?
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Telemedicine	Has a referral system to ensure that suitable cases are included and unsuitable cases directed elsewhere been devised and tested? Has an effective system for case escalation and referral, with appropriate prioritisation according to severity or urgency been developed and tested?
Pre-Clinical	Modifier	Telemedicine	Is there a clear strategy for the integration of the telemedicine tool within existing care pathways and the broader healthcare ecosystem?
Shadow / Experimental	Function	All DHT - General	Has the developer conducted an iterative evaluation process during the experimental/shadow stage, including systematic modification of the DHT or its usage based on performance data and user feedback, and transparently documented these changes along with their impacts?
Shadow / Experimental	Function	All DHT - General	Has the initial risk assessment been updated based on preclinical or early-stage findings, and do the new evaluations identify emerging risks in real-world settings with appropriate mitigation strategies?
Shadow / Experimental	Function	All DHT - General	Have all the modifications of the device been reported and explained to allow a better understanding of the iterative process?
Shadow / Experimental	Function	Data Selection and Reporting	Has the developer submitted data on the technical performance of the device under live clinical conditions during the experimental stage?
Shadow / Experimental	Function	Diagnostic	Is there evidence of any calibrations to local data, allowing a better integration into the system during the tests? Has a simulated stress test been conducted to demonstrate robust interoperability with other DHTs in the work system?
Shadow / Experimental	Function	Disability Alleviation	Were individuals with disabilities included early to assess accessibility and real-world relevance? Was informed consent tailored to participants' communication or cognitive needs? Were early usability outcomes and adverse events shared transparently?
Shadow / Experimental	Function	Disability Alleviation	Was the system integrated into daily care routines and evaluated for real-world support settings?
Shadow / Experimental	Function	Prevention	Has the effectiveness of the device in preventing the onset or the worsening of the targeted pathology been assessed in a series of cases?
Shadow / Experimental	Function	Prevention	Is there evidence showing when any changes occurred during the case series, and presenting case-sequential data so that the effects of all iterative improvements on performance can be appreciated?
Shadow / Experimental	Function	Sensing/Monitoring	Has the system been integrated into the clinical workflow and tested in a real-world setting for technical and procedural compatibility?

Shadow / Experimental	Function	Treatment Recommendation	Were initial users selected to minimise risk and assess clinical validity in real-world practice? Was the consent adapted to reflect the decision-support role of the DHT and its limitations? Were treatment decisions and clinical outcomes reported sequentially and transparently?
Shadow / Experimental	Function	Treatment Conduct	Were appropriate candidates selected for the first-in-human use based on risk, benefit, and diversity criteria? Were enhanced consent processes used, ensuring participants were informed about investigational nature and risks? Was comprehensive reporting of the first-in-human experience, including adverse events and protocol deviations, provided?
Shadow / Experimental	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Was output stable under different conditions of use when using local data? Changes in data distribution, format of input data, or robustness of the missing data handling process can all influence performance when transitioning to local data.
Shadow / Experimental	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Was the DHT performance on local data assessed? Are changes from <i>in silico</i> performance and adequation of the results with the intended purpose adequately discussed in the report?
Shadow / Experimental	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Were any differences in performance on local data for pre-specified subgroups, especially those believed to be subject to performance biases, identified? Does the report discuss these differences and how they compare to those observed during <i>in silico</i> testing?
Shadow / Experimental	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Are there any substantive differences between the local and training population, which would warrant calibration or model re-training on local data?
Shadow / Experimental	Modifier	Autonomy	Were the autonomous functions tested first in low-risk or simulated environments before human use? Was it clearly communicated what level of autonomy the system has and how users can override it? Did the first-in-human report include unexpected, automated behaviours or override scenarios?
Shadow / Experimental	Modifier	Human Factors	Was an error analysis conducted?
Shadow / Experimental	Modifier	Human Factors	Has a user experience test in a typical live clinical use environment use been conducted?
Shadow / Experimental	Modifier	Human Factors	Was an iterative evaluation and improvement phase carried out until all the usability and safety goals were met?
Shadow / Experimental	Modifier	Human Factors	Was the integration of the new DHT into the workflow assessed with naturalistic observations, interviews, document review and debriefing?
Shadow / Experimental	Modifier	Interoperability	Was the DHT trialed in environments with varying infrastructure to test compatibility? Were participants informed about data exchange between systems and possible integration failures? Was interoperability success or failure documented during 3 - Early Clinical integration?
Shadow / Experimental	Modifier	Interoperability	Has integration with heterogeneous clinical systems been demonstrated, including real-time data exchange and compatibility with local infrastructure?
Shadow / Experimental	Modifier	Telemedicine	Have the developers designed and implemented procedures to trouble shoot technical problem in the distance and deliver the necessary updates?
Shadow / Experimental	Modifier	Telemedicine	Is remote patient care adequately integrated into existing schedules for in person patient care? Is sufficient time planned for healthcare professional aside their in person clinical practice?
Shadow / Experimental	Modifier	Telemedicine	Was the impact of the telemedicine tool on the patient mental wellbeing assessed and possible disruption to every day's life identified?
Early Clinical	Function	All DHT - General	Does the nature of the DHT suggest that operator learning curves are a concern? If so, have these been studied using appropriate statistical methods?
Early Clinical	Function	All DHT - General	Are there any analyses of the evolution of user trust into the device?
Early Clinical	Function	All DHT - General	Has the DHT's clinical performance been evaluated prospectively in diverse, real-world clinical environments, including analysis across representative subgroups and consideration of setting-specific variability?

Early Clinical	Function	All DHT - General	Has the developer assessed user learning curves and evolving trust in the DHT during early clinical use, using appropriate quantitative and qualitative methods to evaluate user proficiency, confidence, and adaptation over time?
Early Clinical	Function	All DHT - General	Have updates or refinements been made to the DHT during Early clinical use in response to observed issues, user feedback, or real-world deployment challenges, and are these changes transparently documented?
Early Clinical	Function	Disability Alleviation	Was usability tested in clinical environments using task-based testing and iterative design changes?
Early Clinical	Function	Disability Alleviation	Was acceptance of the DHT among people with disabilities measured using validated instruments?
Early Clinical	Function	Prognostic	Has the developer documented further modifications based on data analysis?
Early Clinical	Function	Prognostic	Were patients consulted regarding usability and transparency of prognostic output during clinical evaluation?
Early Clinical	Function	Sensing/Monitoring	Has patient satisfaction, ease of use, and perceived usefulness been measured during clinical deployment?
Early Clinical	Function	Treatment Conduct	Have system ergonomics and user-system interaction been studied in the clinical environment?
Early Clinical	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Are changes from shadow mode performance and the adequation of these results with the claimed clinical utility adequately discussed in the report? In the case of adaptive AI, was the performance evolution over time also assessed?
Early Clinical	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Were any differences in performance under live conditions identified for pre-specified subgroups and subgroups prone to performance biases? Does the report discuss these differences and how they compare to those observed during shadow mode evaluation? In the case of adaptive AI, was the evolution of performance difference between subgroups over time reported?
Early Clinical	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Were the occurrence and causes of errors thoroughly analysed and explained? In the case of adaptive AI, was the evolution of error occurrence and causes over time also reported?
Early Clinical	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Is the relationship between the AI output and actual clinical decision making explained quantitatively and qualitatively?
Early Clinical	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Was the level of human-computer agreement evaluated? If an important difference exists between the proposed DHT output and final human decision, how was the DHT performance reported?
Early Clinical	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Were the AI oversight mechanisms and AI-human hand-over procedures in case of malfunctions adequately assessed?
Early Clinical	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Was the robustness of the risk mitigation strategy developed at the previous stage re-evaluated, considering the additional complexity of human factors under live use?
Early Clinical	Modifier	Autonomy	Was the perceived safety and control over autonomous functions assessed from the patient perspective?
Early Clinical	Modifier	Human Factors	Has the user experience of the product been evaluated with a large sample of participants?
Early Clinical	Modifier	Human Factors	Was a new error analysis conducted at this stage, updating previous assessments?
Early Clinical	Modifier	Human Factors	Have the integration and impact of the new device into the pre-existing healthcare system been assessed? This assessment should provide analysis of the changes in the work system after introduction of the new DHT
Early Clinical	Modifier	Telemedicine	Was the quality of care provided by the telemedicine technology assessed using valid criteria in a large representative cohort of patients from a range of institutions?
Early Clinical	Modifier	Telemedicine	Has the compliance of patients with advice and recommendations made by healthcare practitioners via telemedicine been evaluated?
Early Clinical	Modifier	Telemedicine	Was the level of engagement and interaction of the patients with the telemedicine DHT assessed, using adequate metrics?
Early Clinical	Modifier	Telemedicine	Has patient access to the telemedicine resource been studied in real world settings? Could digital exclusion bias estimates of its' effectiveness?
Early Clinical	Modifier	Telemedicine	Has timely access to in-person medical care been studied for patients identified as requiring it via telemedicine?

Comparative Study	Function	All DHT - General	Has the cost-effectiveness of the DHT been evaluated, considering both direct and indirect costs and benefits, using standard health economic measures such as QALYs or ICER?
Comparative Study	Function	All DHT - General	Has the DHT's clinical effectiveness been compared with current standard of care using robust study designs (e.g., RCTs), with clear reporting of relevant outcomes and subgroup effects?
Comparative Study	Function	Diagnostic	Have studies compared the diagnostic accuracy of the DHT with the current standard of care or other competing technologies with the same functions? Were these studies conducted using the two methods in parallel on the same patient group, with users blinded to the results of one test when conducting the other.
Comparative Study	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Were the occurrences and causes of errors when used at larger scale thoroughly analysed by the developers?
Comparative Study	Modifier	Human Factors	Were the differences in the organisation and uses of new and pre-existing devices assessed?
Comparative Study	Modifier	Telemedicine	Was the difference in outpatient visits and admission rate between patients using the telemedicine DHT and the comparator group reported?
Comparative Study	Modifier	Telemedicine	Given the important influence of socio-economic status on health outcome outside healthcare settings, was the comparative analysis controlled for socio-economic status? Were significant differences in performance between socio-economic groups identified?
Surveillance	Function	All DHT - General	Are there surveillance mechanisms in place to detect late or rare adverse events associated with the DHT, supported by long-term follow-up studies or real-world data, and are corrective actions taken when necessary?
Surveillance	Function	All DHT - General	Are DHT updates—including algorithmic, software, or functional changes—systematically tracked and evaluated for their impact on performance, safety, and compliance with intended use?
Surveillance	Function	Data Selection and Reporting	Is there evidence on how population shifts affect the device's use and effectiveness?
Surveillance	Function	Data Selection and Reporting	Is there evidence for any expansion of the device's use beyond its intended indications?
Surveillance	Function	Data Selection and Reporting	Is there evidence of how the device modifies care pathways?
Surveillance	Function	Data Selection and Reporting	Has the developer provided a reassessment of the scalability, generalisability, sustainability, and long-term viability of the device's business model?
Surveillance	Function	Diagnostic	Has any analysis of diagnostic accuracy in routine use been reported? Is there any evidence of changes in performance over time, in particular locations or in specific subgroups of patients?
Surveillance	Function	Diagnostic	Are data available to evaluate the influence of prevalence changes, population shifts and indication creep on diagnostic accuracy?
Surveillance	Function	Diagnostic	The effects of changes in diagnostic pathways should be considered when investigating apparent changes in test accuracy.
Surveillance	Function	Disability Alleviation	Were there documented shifts in clinician behavior, treatment patterns, or service provision after DHT implementation?
Surveillance	Function	Disability Alleviation	Has the developer monitored for use in populations or conditions not originally intended by the DHT?
Surveillance	Function	Disability Alleviation	Has the developer provided data or justification to evaluate whether changes in user demographics or health system demands might alter DHT performance or usage?
Surveillance	Function	Disability Alleviation	Has the developer provided data monitoring how the device modifies care pathways?

Surveillance	Function	Prevention	Have the effects of changes in other influences on disease risk or harm exposure been considered when investigating apparent changes in the effectiveness of preventive DHTs ?
Surveillance	Function	Prognostic	Is there evidence of changes in clinician performance and decision making related to the device? Can this be linked to outcome changes?
Surveillance	Function	Prognostic	Has the developer provided data monitoring any expansion of the device’s use beyond its intended indications?
Surveillance	Function	Prognostic	Is there evidence to allow assessment on how population shifts may affect the device’s use and effectiveness?
Surveillance	Function	Treatment Conduct	Has the DHT’s influence on clinical behavior or workflow been evaluated post-deployment?
Surveillance	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Does any difference in performance between pre-specified subgroups and subgroups prone to performance biases appear or worsen over time?
Surveillance	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	<i>Are changes in the target population over time monitored? This can be due to evolving comorbidities profile, the effect of new diagnostic methods, or changing health policies.</i>
Surveillance	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	<i>Are changes in the indication of use over time monitored? These changes can result from wider use in clinical settings or changing practice.</i>
Surveillance	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Are any software updates, both in term of processing or information display, and their subsequent impact on performance or use transparently reported?
Surveillance	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	Are AI oversight mechanisms and AI to human hand-over procedures monitored and consistent over time?
Surveillance	Modifier	Artificial intelligence	For adaptive AI, is adversarial testing regularly conducted over time and are the results demonstrating stability of the AI outputs?
Surveillance	Modifier	Autonomy	Is there monitoring in place to detect whether clinicians are applying the DHT in unapproved settings or indications?
Surveillance	Modifier	Autonomy	Is there a mechanism to detect and evaluate the effect of shifting populations on the appropriateness or safety of the DHT?
Surveillance	Modifier	Human Factors	Has the impact of the new DHT on workflow and workload been analysed in large scale studies using data and methods which allow valid assessment across a large population?
Surveillance	Modifier	Human Factors	Has an assessment of changes in the organisation of work in relevant institutions been carried out using such methods?
Surveillance	Modifier	Human Factors	Has an analysis of the number of errors and failure in DHT use been conducted which attempts to describe experience accurately across a large population?
Surveillance	Modifier	Telemedicine	Was the long-term added value in terms of healthcare system resource use evaluated?

ANNEX 2: Guidance for the online lifecycle assessment tool

To facilitate the practical application of the life cycle-based evaluation model, the ASSESS-DHT framework incorporates a digital automation tool to simplify the task of finding the appropriate recommendations for a given DHT. The interface allows users to specify the life cycle stage, functional purpose, system modifiers, and risk level of their DHT, and automatically generates tailored evaluation recommendations and export them in a PDF format. This greatly reduces user workload and encourages consistent use of the recommendations. It is intended for use by developers, HTA analysts, and policy makers to support planning, documentation, and submission of DHT assessment. Figures 1,2 and 3 illustrate the functioning of the automated tool.

The screenshot displays the landing screen of the ASSESS-DHT Recommendation Generator. On the left, a vertical sidebar contains the ASSESS-DHT logo and a 'Navigate' menu with three options: 'Recommendation Generator' (selected with a red dot), 'Lifecycle Description', and 'Functions & Modifiers'. Below the menu is the text 'ASSESS-DHT Framework v6.1 © 2025'. The main content area features a large heading 'Recommendation Generator' with a clipboard icon. Below the heading are three dropdown menus labeled 'Lifecycle Stage(s)', 'Device Function(s)', and 'System Modifier(s)', each with the text 'Choose an option' and a downward arrow. A light blue banner at the top right of the main area contains the text 'Start by selecting filters to see recommendations.'

Landing screen of the ASSESS-DHT Recommendation Generator

Lifecycle Stage(s)

Choose an option

- Preclinical
- Experimental/Local Validation
- Early Clinical
- Comparative Study
- Long-term Study

Device Function(s)

Choose an option

- All DHT - General
- Data Selection and Reporting
- Diagnostic
- Disability Alleviation
- Prevention
- Prognostic
- Sensing/Monitoring
- Treatment Recommendation

System Modifier(s)

Choose an option

- Artificial intelligence
- Autonomy
- Human Factors
- Interoperability
- Telemedicine

Dropdown menus

Recommendation Generator

Lifecycle Stage(s)

Preclinical x

Device Function(s)

Diagnostic x Sensing/Monitor... x

System Modifier(s)

Artificial intellige... x Interoperability x

✔ Total recommendations: 16

✦ Preclinical (16 items)

Function: All DHT - General

Is there a complete and precise description of the device with its technical specifications, which would allow the replication of the first tests in laboratory conditions?

Function: All DHT - General

Has a software development lifecycle that is compliant with standard practices been completed for Software as Medical Device?

Function: All DHT - General

Has a data management plan been put in place to increase data security and prevent the risk of data breach or loss?

Function: All DHT - General

Has a comprehensive risk assessment been conducted addressing device-specific, user-related, and data-related risks, including safety, reliability, digital inclusion, and ethical considerations, with clearly defined mitigation strategies tailored to the intended use and target population?

Function: All DHT - General

Has the developer provided evidence that the device fulfills its intended technical functions reliably and accurately, under expected conditions and across relevant scenarios, including compliance with applicable standards and performance expectations specific to its technological and functional design

Example of function- and modifier-specific recommendation

After consulting the ASSESS-DHT recommendations via the online automated tool, users can analyse the available evidence against the matrix recommendations for the relevant stage (and prior stages). This includes mapping the types and quality of data available—such as usability studies, RCTs, or real-world data—to the stages where they are most relevant. This structured analysis ensures that gaps are not only identified but contextualised within a broader developmental

trajectory. It also determines whether essential questions for the current or previous stages have been adequately addressed. If not, the HTA can highlight these gaps and recommend further research, possibly under adaptive approval conditions or post-market evidence generation requirements.

ANNEX 3: D3.1 Short Data Protection and Privacy Checklist

GDPR article	Criteria	Implementation
Article 5 Principles Relating to Processing of Personal Data	Personal data must be processed lawfully, fairly, and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject.	Ensure that all data processing activities have a legal basis under GDPR. Provide clear and accessible information to data subjects about how their data is being processed. Implement transparency measures such as privacy notices and consent forms
Article 6 Lawfulness of Processing	The data subject must have given consent to the processing of their personal data for one or more specific purposes.	Obtain explicit consent from data subjects before processing their data for example by ticking a box Inform data subjects about their right to withdraw consent and how to do so. Participants / data subjects must be assured that deciding not to participate or withdrawing from the data processing activity will not affect their care in any way or prejudice them otherwise
Article 8 Conditions Applicable to Child's Consent in Relation to Information Society Services	The processing of a child's personal data is lawful if the child is at least 16 years old.	Implement age verification mechanisms to ensure the child is at least 16 years old before processing their personal data.
Article 9 Processing of Special Categories of Personal Data	Processing of special categories of personal data is prohibited unless specific conditions are met.	Justification for special categories of personal data must be defined and compatible with the selected lawful basis and purposes of the data processing
Article 12 Transparent Information, Communication, and Modalities for the Exercise of the	The controller must take appropriate measures to provide any information and any communication relating to processing to the data subject in a concise, transparent, intelligible,	Develop clear and accessible privacy notices and communication materials. Use plain language and avoid legal jargon. Ensure that information is easily accessible, such as through websites or mobile apps

Rights of the Data Subject	and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language.	
Article 15 Right of Access by the Data Subject	If personal data are being processed, the data subject has the right to access the data and the following information:	<p>Establish a data access policy.</p> <p>Develop and provide privacy notices that include all required information:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The purposes of the processing. 2. The categories of personal data concerned. 3. The recipients or categories of recipients to whom the personal data have been or will be disclosed, particularly recipients in third countries or international organisations. 4. The envisaged period for which the personal data will be stored, or the criteria used to determine that period. 5. The existence of the right to request rectification or erasure of personal data, restriction of processing, or to object to processing. 6. The right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority. 7. The source of the personal data, if not collected from the data subject. 8. The existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, and meaningful information about the logic involved and the significance and consequences of such processing.
Article 16 Right to Rectification	The data subject has the right to obtain from the controller the rectification of inaccurate personal data concerning them.	<p>Develop processes to handle rectification requests from data subjects.</p> <p>Ensure that inaccurate data is corrected promptly upon request.</p>
Article 17 Right to Erasure (Right to Be Forgotten)	The data subject has the right to obtain from the controller the erasure of personal data concerning them without undue delay.	<p>Develop processes to handle erasure requests from data subjects.</p> <p>Ensure that personal data is erased promptly upon request, unless an exception applies</p>
Article 18 Right to Restriction of Processing	The data subject may request the restriction of processing when the accuracy of the personal data is contested.	<p>Develop processes to handle restriction requests (inaccurate, unlawful, pending verification legitimate grounds) from data subjects.</p> <p>Establish a policy defining that the data subjects can request to erase their data.</p>

		<p>Ensure that processing is restricted promptly upon request, unless an exception applies.</p> <p>Ensure that the data subject shall be informed before the restriction of processing is lifted.</p>
<p>Article 24 Responsibility of the Controller</p>	<p>The controller must implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure and demonstrate compliance with the GDPR.</p>	<p>Develop and enforce data protection policies and procedures. Conduct regular audits and assessments to ensure compliance.</p> <p>Maintain documentation of compliance efforts.</p>
<p>Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default</p>	<p>The controller must implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to integrate data protection principles into processing activities.</p>	<p>Conduct data protection impact assessments (DPIAs) for new processing activities.</p> <p>Design systems and processes with data protection in mind from the outset</p>
<p>Article 26 Joint Controllers</p>	<p>Where two or more controllers jointly determine the purposes and means of processing, they must determine their respective responsibilities for compliance.</p>	<p>Establish clear agreements outlining the responsibilities of each joint controller.</p> <p>Ensure that data subjects are informed about the essence of the arrangement.</p>
<p>Article 28 Processor</p>	<p>The processor must process personal data only on documented instructions from the controller.</p>	<p>Establish clear contracts with processors outlining their obligations.</p> <p>Ensure that processors comply with the controller's instructions and GDPR requirements.</p>
<p>Article 29 Processing Under the Authority of the Controller or Processor</p>	<p>The processor and any person acting under the authority of the controller or processor must process personal data only on instructions from the controller.</p>	<p>Ensure that all personnel involved in data processing are aware of and comply with the controller's instructions.</p> <p>Implement training programs to educate personnel about their responsibilities under GDPR.</p>

<p>Article 30</p> <p>Records of Processing Activities</p>	<p>Controllers must maintain records of processing activities under their responsibility.</p>	<p>Develop and maintain comprehensive records of all data processing activities.</p> <p>Include information such as the purposes of processing, categories of data subjects and personal data, recipients, data transfers, and security measures.</p> <p>Ensure that the records are made available to the supervisory authority on request.</p>
<p>Article 32</p> <p>Security of Processing</p>	<p>The controller and the processor must implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk.</p>	<p>Conduct risk assessments to identify potential security threats.</p> <p>Implement measures such as encryption, pseudonymisation, access controls, and regular security audits</p>
<p>Article 33</p> <p>Notification of a Personal Data Breach to the Supervisory Authority</p>	<p>The controller must notify the supervisory authority of a personal data breach without undue delay and, where feasible, not later than 72 hours after becoming aware of it.</p>	<p>Develop and implement a data breach response plan.</p> <p>Ensure that all staff are trained to recognise and report data breaches promptly</p>
<p>Article 34</p> <p>Communication of a Personal Data Breach to the Data Subject</p>	<p>The controller must communicate a personal data breach to the data subject without undue delay when the breach is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals.</p>	<p>Develop procedures for assessing the risk level of data breaches.</p> <p>Ensure that affected data subjects are informed promptly and provided with relevant information and guidance.</p>
<p>Article 35</p> <p>Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)</p>	<p>The controller must carry out a DPIA when processing is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals.</p>	<p>Identify processing activities that require a DPIA.</p> <p>Develop and implement a DPIA process that includes risk assessment, mitigation measures, and documentation also including risk related to automated processing, large scale processing of data related to criminal convictions and offences, etc)</p>
<p>Article 37</p> <p>Designation of the</p>	<p>The controller and the processor must designate a DPO in certain circumstances, such as when</p>	<p>Assess whether your organisation is required to designate a DPO.</p> <p>Appoint a qualified individual as the DPO ensure they have the necessary resources and authority.</p>

<p>Data Protection Officer (DPO)</p>	<p>processing is carried out by a public authority or involves large-scale processing of special categories of data.</p>	<p>Provide a DPO policy describing the tasks of the DPO Provide clear contact information for the DPO on the organisation's website and in privacy notices</p>
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ANNEX 4: Data quality assessment criteria for Data Quality Management

The use of AI		
Criteria	Details	Assessment
Does the organisation specify the AI algorithm used and its data quality requirements?	Verify if the organisation documents the type of AI algorithm being employed (e.g., supervised, unsupervised, semi-supervised, reinforcement learning) and ensures that the data quality requirements align with the specific needs of the algorithm (e.g. labelled data for supervised learning).	Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide the documentation detailing the algorithm and its corresponding data quality requirements, such as project plans, technical specifications, or data quality models.</i>
Is labelling required for the selected AI algorithms?	Assess whether the organisation has identified the need for labelled datasets for semi-supervised learning tasks, based on the objectives of the AI application.	Yes/No, <i>If yes, verify that the organisation has a documented labelling requirement, supported by use case specifications or project documentation.</i>
Are roles and responsibilities for labelling defined and documented?	Assess whether the organisation assigns specific roles (e.g., annotators, inspectors...) and responsibilities in the labelling process.	Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide supporting evidence such as organisational charts, tasks assignment documents, or job descriptions.</i>
Does the organisation employ quality control measures for labelling?	Verify whether the organisation implements systematic quality control for labelling, such as random sampling, stratified sampling, or full inspection.	Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide examples of quality control processes, inspection results, or error rate reports.</i>
Are labelling tools or platforms aligned with data security and compliance requirements?	Check if the organisation ensures that labelling tools and platforms support essential functions (e.g., metadata creation, traceability) and comply with data security and privacy regulations.	Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide examples of tool configurations, security policies, or compliance audit reports.</i>

<p>Is the organisation mitigating bias in labelled datasets?</p>	<p>Assess whether the organisation implements strategies to minimise bias in labelled datasets (e.g., diverse annotators, automated validations, bias audits).</p>	<p>Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide evidence such as bias mitigation plans, audit results, or annotator diversity reports.</i></p>
<p>Are labelling processes and datasets documented for transparency?</p>	<p>Verify whether the organisation maintains detailed documentation of the labelling process, revisions, and metadata for traceability.</p>	<p>Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide examples of documentation, including labelling logs, metadata schemas, or audit trails.</i></p>
<p>Does the organisation periodically review and update labelling specifications?</p>	<p>Check if labelling guidelines and processes are regularly reviewed and updated to align with evolving use cases and quality requirements.</p>	<p>Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide evidence of versioned guidelines, review schedules, or change logs.</i></p>

ANNEX 5: Data Quality checklist

Uniqueness			
Pre-check (linking with Annex 4):			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has the developer indicated that this dimension is relevant for their application? - Has the developer defined thresholds or expectations for this dimension? - Has the developer provided documentation or evidence of actions taken (related to Annex 4)? 			
If the answer to all is “no” → Skip or flag the dimension			
Criteria	Details	Assessment	HTA relevance
Are checks conducted to identify duplicated rows?	Assess whether mechanisms exist to identify and flag rows with duplication. This could include duplicate identifiers, identical field entries, or near-duplicate records.	Yes/No If yes, describe the scope (e.g., all fields vs key fields) and frequency of these checks. Provide logs, schedules, or audit plans as evidence.	Include – Relevant for HTA if the developer has declared in Annex 4 that uniqueness was assessed. It helps HTA “doers” verify whether core data quality checks were performed, even without raw data.
What methods or tools are used to detect duplicate data?	Specify tools, algorithms, or techniques used for detecting duplicates, such as rule-based systems, or manual reviews.	Yes/No If yes, list tools (e.g., Python/R libraries, SQL queries, data matching tools).	Exclude – This is too technical and depends on access to developer systems or raw data. Not feasible or useful for HTA teams without deep technical access.
What criteria are used to classify duplicate data?	Define the rules applied for duplicate detection, such as exact matches, partial matches, of specific use case uniqueness rules.	Provide documentation of criteria or thresholds, such as “similarity score > 90%.” Include examples where possible.	Exclude – Requires access to internal logic and source data, which HTA evaluators generally don’t have. Also unlikely to be documented in a way HTA teams can use.
What steps are taken to address duplicate rows?	Outline strategies for resolving duplicates, such as merging records, deleting redundant	Provide workflows, policies, or scripts used to address duplicates.	Include (conditionally) – Can be useful for HTA “doers” if the developer documented processes in Annex 4. It shows whether duplicates were systematically addressed, supporting transparency.

	entries, or adding unique identifiers.		
How are duplicate-related errors mitigated?	Describe error mitigation strategies, such as data deduplication scripts, or automated alerts.	Provide examples of applied techniques, logs of resolved issues, or policy updates to address recurring duplicate issues.	Include (if documented) – Valuable for understanding longer-term quality management. HTA evaluators can use this if there’s supporting evidence in Annex 4.

Completeness

Pre-check (linking with Annex 4):

- Has the developer indicated that this dimension is relevant for their application?
- Has the developer defined thresholds or expectations for this dimension?
- Has the developer provided documentation or evidence of actions taken (related to Annex 4)?

If the answer to all is “no” → Skip or flag the dimension

Criteria	Details	Assessment	HTA relevance
Are there processes in place to identify missing data?	Evaluate whether mechanisms, such as data validation checks or reports, are in place to identify when essential or conditional variables are missing. Ensure these processes are regularly applied to incoming or existing datasets.	Yes/No <i>If yes, describe tools or methods used to identify missing data. Provide examples of validation logs or missing data reports.</i>	Include – Highly relevant if completeness was documented in Annex 4. HTA evaluators can verify that the DHT team had mechanisms for detecting missing values, which is critical for judging data quality.
What processes are in place to address missing data?	Assess the strategies or workflows used to resolve missing variables. This may include manual data entry, re-collection, imputation, or data augmentation.	Provide examples of corrective action taken to address missing data, such as policies, procedures, or logs.	Include (if documented) – Useful if high-level strategies (e.g., imputation) are described in Annex 4 or other documentation. Allows HTA to assess whether missingness was actively managed.
Are there mechanisms to determine the type of missing data?	Verify whether processes are in place to classify missing data into categories such as missing completely at random (MCAR), missing at random (MAR), or not missing at random (NMAR), as these may impact bias in analyses or downstream decisions.	Yes/No <i>If yes, describe how missing data is classified, such as through statistical modelling or exploratory data analysis. Provide examples of classification outputs or biases identified.</i>	Exclude – Too technical and assumes access to detailed statistical analyses or raw data. Not generally feasible for HTA “doers” to assess, especially later in the process.
Are there procedures to evaluate and	Assess whether there are systematic processes to verify that the dataset covers the intended population,	Yes/No	Include – Coverage evaluation (i.e. checking whether all subpopulations, timeframes, or required data types are present) is

ensure dataset coverage?	timeframes, or scenarios. Ensure coverage reviews occur regularly and are well-documented.	<i>If yes, describe the procedures and provide examples of coverage evaluation reports or analyses.</i>	critical to HTA. Can be reviewed based on summaries or documentation, not raw data.
	Evaluate whether mechanisms exist to identify gaps in dataset coverage (e.g., unrepresented populations, timeframes) and whether there are defined strategies for filling these gaps.	Provide examples of actions taken to address coverage gaps, such as targeted data collection, augmentation with external sources, or exclusion of incomplete records. Include documentation of actions or results.	Include (if documented) – Can be useful if the developer has flagged and responded to missing populations or data gaps. HTA can assess this only if supported by Annex 4 content (e.g. population coverage plans).

Consistency

Pre-check (linking with Annex 4):

- Has the developer indicated that this dimension is relevant for their application?
- Has the developer defined thresholds or expectations for this dimension?
- Has the developer provided documentation or evidence of actions taken (related to Annex 4)?

If the answer to all is “no” → Skip or flag the dimension

Criteria	Details	Assessment	HTA relevance
Are syntactic consistency checks conducted?	Evaluate whether checks enforce consistent data types, formats, and structures (e.g., integer vs. string, consistent date formats).	Yes/No If yes, describe tools (e.g., schema validation tools, Python scripts). Provide error logs or validation reports as evidence.	Include – If the DHT developer documented consistency checks in Annex 4, this is a clear and assessable signal of quality assurance. HTA bodies can verify whether expected formats/types were enforced.
Are predefined templates or schemas used?	Determine whether data schemas or dictionaries ensure uniformity in collection, storage, and processing.	Yes/No If yes, provide examples of schemas or templates used.	Include (if documented) – Useful for HTA if the use of data dictionaries or standards is declared in Annex 4. Shows structured, standardised data collection but relies on accessible documentation.
Are checks conducted for distribution consistency?	Verify whether the dataset’s statistical distributions align with expected patterns. Look for anomalies like skewness or unexpected clustering.	Yes/No If yes, describe techniques (e.g., histograms, statistical tests). Provide examples of tools used, such as R/Python libraries or visualisation dashboards.	Exclude – Assessing statistical distribution requires access to raw data and technical analysis, which HTA “doers” typically don’t have.
Are outliers detected and evaluated?	Assess whether outlier detection methods (e.g., IQR, Z-scores) are applied systematically.	Yes/No If yes, describe methods used and provide logs or visualisations of flagged outliers.	Exclude – Assessing outliers requires access to raw data and technical analysis, which HTA “doers” typically don’t have.

<p>How are consistency errors mitigated?</p>	<p>Describe corrective actions for identified inconsistencies, such as schema updates, reprocessing workflows, or user prompts to correct data.</p>	<p>Provide examples of actions taken and tools used to enforce corrections. Include logs or documentation of workflows.</p>	<p>Include (if documented) – Only include if the DHT team has provided clear documentation in Annex 4. Helps HTA assess whether detected issues were acted upon but depends on transparency from developers.</p>
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Correctness

Pre-check (linking with Annex 4):

- Has the developer indicated that this dimension is relevant for their application?
- Has the developer defined thresholds or expectations for this dimension?
- Has the developer provided documentation or evidence of actions taken (related to Annex 4)?

If the answer to all is “no” → Skip or flag the dimension

Criteria	Details	Assessment	HTA relevance
Are data precision requirements clearly defined?	Verify whether precision requirements (e.g., decimal places, time intervals) are documented for critical fields.	Yes/No <i>If yes, provide documentation of standards, such as data dictionaries.</i>	Include – Relevant if the DHT developer has stated in Annex 4 that precision matters for their use case. HTA assessors can verify whether required resolution (e.g., decimal places) was considered.
How is data precision being assessed?	Assess whether data precision is evaluated using tools, validation rules, or automated checks to ensure alignment with specified requirements.	Yes/No <i>If yes, provide evidence such as validation reports, automated system logs, or quality dashboards.</i>	Include (if documented) – Useful only if assessment processes are described. Feasible for HTA teams to review if summaries or dashboards are provided.
How are precision-related errors resolved?	Describe processes for addressing precision errors, such as recalibration of input systems or applying transformations.	Provide examples of these processes, such as scripts or re-collection policies.	Include (if documented) – May offer insights into the robustness of the development process, but only assessable if developers disclose methods in Annex 4
Are granularity requirements clearly specified?	Verify whether the required level of detail for each variable is documented (e.g., specific measurements vs. broad categories).	Yes/No <i>If yes, provide documentation specifying granularity standards.</i>	Include – Like precision, this is relevant if granularity (e.g., detailed versus categorised data) was defined by the developer. HTA teams can assess the alignment between granularity and intended use.

<p>How is data granularity being assessed?</p>	<p>Verify whether the required level of detail for each variable is documented (e.g., individual points vs. aggregated categories).</p>	<p>Provide examples of assessment tools, reports, or manual review processes used for granularity checks.</p>	<p>Exclude – This usually requires access to the data itself or technical outputs, which HTA bodies don't have. Not practical without developer input.</p>
<p>How are granularity-related errors resolved?</p>	<p>Describe how granularity issues (e.g., overly aggregated or overly detailed data) are identified and addressed, such as re-aggregation or disaggregation.</p>	<p>Provide documentation of processes, including guidelines, error logs, or tools used to resolve granularity issues.</p>	<p>Include (if documented) – Could be helpful if developer describes re-aggregation, data transformation or review actions, but again only if disclosed in Annex 4 or other accessible material.</p>

Timeliness			
<p>Pre-check (linking with Annex 4):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has the developer indicated that this dimension is relevant for their application? - Has the developer defined thresholds or expectations for this dimension? - Has the developer provided documentation or evidence of actions taken (related to Annex 4)? <p>If the answer to all is “no” → Skip or flag the dimension</p>			
Criteria	Details	Assessment	HTA relevance
How is the relevance of the data collection time evaluated?	Determine whether the organisation periodically reviews the appropriateness of data collection intervals. Ensure that datasets remain reflective of current conditions and meet the needs of their intended use.	Yes/No <i>If yes, provide examples of reviews or evaluations conducted. Include documentation of adjusted data collection schedules or any reports analysing timeliness.</i>	Include – Directly relevant for HTA if the developer in Annex 4 has flagged time sensitivity. HTA “doers” can review whether the data is recent and appropriate to current clinical content.
What steps are taken to address delays in data collection?	Describe the actions implemented to identify and mitigate delays in data collection. Examples include optimizing workflows, automating processes, or increasing data collection capacity by allocating additional resources.	Provide examples of corrective actions, such as revised workflows, new tools implemented, or documented policies addressing delays.	Include (if documented) – HTA can assess whether collection workflows were optimised, but only if the developer shares planning or mitigation efforts in Annex 4.
Is the time taken to process the data assessed and optimised?	Evaluate whether the organisation systematically monitors data processing times and takes steps to ensure efficiency. Assess whether delays in processing affect the dataset’s usability, particularly for time-sensitive	Yes/No <i>If yes, describe tools or techniques (e.g., time tracking systems, log analysis, bottleneck identification) used to monitor and optimise processing times.</i>	Include (if documented) – Valuable if the developer explains data processing delays and their impact. Can support judgment of operational quality, though hard to assess without clear documentation.

	<p>applications like real-time decision-making.</p>		
<p>What mechanisms are in place to expedite data processing?</p>	<p>Assess whether procedures, tools, or workflows are in place to minimise processing delays. Examples include implementing batch processing, parallel computation, or cloud-based data pipelines. Ensure these methods maintain data quality standards while improving speed.</p>	<p>Provide documentation of implemented strategies or tools (e.g., automated processing systems, optimised workflows). Include examples of observed improvements or case studies.</p>	<p>Exclude – Too operational and system-specific. HTA teams typically cannot evaluate internal IT infrastructure or workflow performance unless already summarised by the developer.</p>

Stability

Pre-check (linking with Annex 4):

- Has the developer indicated that this dimension is relevant for their application?
- Has the developer defined thresholds or expectations for this dimension?
- Has the developer provided documentation or evidence of actions taken (related to Annex 4)?

If the answer to all is “no” → Skip or flag the dimension

Criteria	Details	Assessment	HTA relevance
What processes are in place to identify patient-level stability issues?	Confirm whether processes or tools (e.g., trend analysis, variance checks) are used to detect abnormal fluctuations for individual patients.	Provide details of tools or processes, such as data visualisations, automated alerts, or statistical methods.	Exclude – Requires detailed longitudinal data access and patient-level trend analysis. Not assessable by HTA without raw data. Only suitable for internal quality assurance by developers.
How are patient-level stability issues resolved?	Describe corrective measures for patient-level instability, such as recalibrating measurement devices, re-validating patient records, or investigating external factors (e.g., data entry errors).	Provide examples of corrective actions taken and their outcomes. Include policies or logs showing how instability was addressed.	Exclude – Same reason as above: actions taken to fix fluctuations in individual data points are not visible to HTA and too technical for this stage of evaluation.
What processes are in place to detect cross-patient stability issues?	Confirm whether tools or workflows are applied to identify unexpected variations across patients.	Provide documentation of tools used and examples of issues identified.	Include (if documented) – Could be useful if aggregate-level trends and quality assurance reports are provided by the developer. Otherwise, not feasible.
How are cross-patient stability issues resolved?	Describe actions taken to address cross-patient instability, such as removing outliers, standardising measurement practices, or	Provide examples of resolutions and supporting documentation, such as revised workflows, statistical corrections, or updated data.	Include (if documented) – If summary-level info exists (e.g., documentation on normalisation), this can inform HTA about consistency across populations.

	verifying clinical factors causing deviations.		
What processes are in place to detect dataset-level temporal stability?	Assess whether automated tools, scripts, or dashboards are used to track temporal trends. Confirm whether known patterns or benchmarks are used to validate changes in key variables.	Provide examples of tools and their outputs.	Include – Especially relevant for HTA “doers”. If the developer has analysed data trends over time (e.g. year-to-year diagnosis rates) and documented them, HTA can use this to check validity.
How are temporal stability issues addressed?	Outline corrective measures applied to temporal instabilities, such as recalibrating data collection processes, revising historical data, or incorporating external datasets for validation.	Provide examples of actions taken, such as updates to workflows or augmented datasets. Include documentation of resolved inconsistencies.	Include (if documented) – Can support understanding of whether the DHT still performs reliable over time. Include only if the developer has disclosed corrective actions.
What processes are in place to detect cross-source stability issues?	Confirm whether tools or workflows (e.g., mapping tools, consistency checks) are applied to identify inconsistencies in data collected from multiple sources.	Provide documentation of tools or scripts used to validate cross-source consistency, such as data dictionaries or semantic validation logs.	Include – Important for HTA, especially when DHTs are trained on multi-source datasets. Can be reviewed if the developer provides summaries of harmonisation or integration checks.
How are cross-source stability issues resolved?	Describe the strategies for addressing cross-source inconsistencies, such as reconciling datasets, applying mapping tools, or consulting domain experts.	Provide examples of reconciliations performed, mapping processes used, or actions taken to standardise data.	Include (if documented) – May be included if the developer shares resolution strategies (e.g. mapping inconsistencies between datasets), but not assessable without disclosure in Annex 4.

Contextualisation

Pre-check (linking with Annex 4):

- Has the developer indicated that this dimension is relevant for their application?
- Has the developer defined thresholds or expectations for this dimension?
- Has the developer provided documentation or evidence of actions taken (related to Annex I)?

If the answer to all is “no” → Skip or flag the dimension

Criteria	Details	Assessment	HTA relevance
Is there a process in place to document and review data sources being used.	Verify whether the organisation has a formal process for documenting and periodically reviewing all data sources used in its operations.	Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide evidence such as data source inventories, review reports, or data governance policies.</i>	Include – Highly relevant. If the DHT developer has described data provenance, care context, and metadata in Annex 4, HTA can judge transparency and relevance of the dataset without needing access to raw data.
Are mapping/transformation steps being documented?	Assess whether the organisation documents all mapping and transformation steps applied to datasets, ensuring transparency and reproducibility.	Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide examples such as transformation logs, mapping schemas, or process documentation.</i>	Include (if documented) – Important for understanding how raw data was shaped into final outputs. HTA can review if summaries or process overviews are available in Annex 4. Otherwise, difficult to assess.
Are computable transformations being documented towards traceability?	Determine whether computable (automated) transformations such as data format changes or algorithmic calculations are documented for traceability.	Yes/No <i>If yes, provide examples of logs, scripts, or audit trails generated during automated transformations.</i>	Exclude – Too technical. HTA “doers” typically don’t access or evaluate automated data workflows (e.g., scripts, feature engineering logs).
Are human transformations being documented towards traceability?	Verify whether manual (human) transformations, such as data cleaning or categorisation, are documented to ensure traceability and accountability.	Yes/No <i>If yes, provide evidence such as annotated workflows, transformation logs, or audit records.</i>	Include (if documented) – Potentially relevant if human editing decisions influenced outcomes. Can inform HTA if well explained in documentation but depends on disclosure.

Trustworthiness

Pre-check (linking with Annex 4):

- Has the developer indicated that this dimension is relevant for their application?
- Has the developer defined thresholds or expectations for this dimension?
- Has the developer provided documentation or evidence of actions taken (related to Annex 4)?

If the answer to all is “no” → Skip or flag the dimension

Criteria	Details	Assessment	HTA relevance
Are processes in place to ensure compliance with legal regulations?	Verify whether data handling processes comply with applicable laws and regulations (e.g., GDPR, HIPAA, CCPA). This includes privacy, security, and data-sharing policies.	Yes/No <i>If yes, provide documentation, such as data protection policies, legal audits, or compliance certificates.</i>	Include – Essential for HTA. Can be verified via developer declarations in Annex 4, even without access to raw data.
Are ethical compliance standards applied to data collection and use?	Verify whether ethical principles are followed, such as obtaining informed consent, ensuring fairness and inclusivity, and reducing biases in datasets.	Yes/No <i>If yes, provide evidence, such as consent forms, ethics committee approvals, or demographic audits ensuring inclusivity.</i>	Include – Relevant and expected in HTA evaluations. HTA teams can check for informed consent, inclusivity, and fairness practices based on what the developer reports in Annex 4.
Are recognised standards and data models adhered to?	Assess whether data conforms to established standards (e.g., HL7 FHIR, ICD-10) for interoperability, structural integrity, and semantic correctness.	Yes/No <i>If yes, provide evidence, such as validation reports, compliance logs, or mapping tools ensuring data adherence to standards.</i>	Include – If the developer confirms use of standards, HTA can assess interoperability and semantic reliability. Requires only documented evidence, not raw system access.
Are processes in place to ensure data accessibility for authorised users?	Verify whether data is easily accessible to authorised users while ensuring security and role-based access. Assess whether metadata and supporting documentation (e.g., data dictionaries) are provided to enhance usability.	Yes/No <i>If yes, provide evidence, such as access control logs, metadata repositories, or user feedback surveys.</i>	Include (if documented) – Relevant if the HTA body needs to verify whether data can be audited or reused. Only assessable if the developer shares access management policies.

<p>How are accessibility issues identified and addressed?</p>	<p>Evaluate whether processes exist to detect and resolve accessibility issues, such as missing documentation, technical barriers, or unclear licensing agreements.</p>	<p>Provide examples of resolved accessibility issues, such as updated metadata, revised access permissions, or improved documentation workflows.</p>	<p>Exclude – Often too operational. HTA teams typically don't evaluate internal service structures unless major issues are reported. Better handled by developers internally.</p>
<p>Are licensing agreements documented and enforced?</p>	<p>Verify whether licensing terms, including permissible uses of the data, are documented and communicated clearly to users.</p>	<p>Yes/No <i>If yes, provide documentation of licensing agreements, user agreements, or terms of use.</i></p>	<p>Include (if documented) – May be relevant for HTA if data usage rights affect downstream evidence reuse. Include only if the DHT developer clearly shares this info.</p>
<p>Are processes in place to review and update trustworthiness policies regularly?</p>	<p>Assess whether legal, ethical, and accessibility policies are reviewed periodically to reflect changes in regulations, organisational goals, or user needs.</p>	<p>Yes/No <i>If yes, provide evidence of review schedules, meeting notes, or updated policies.</i></p>	<p>Include (if documented) – Can be helpful to check maturity of data governance. Assessable if developer discloses review procedures or versioned policies.</p>

Representativeness			
<p>Pre-check (linking with Annex 4):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has the developer indicated that this dimension is relevant for their application? - Has the developer defined thresholds or expectations for this dimension? - Has the developer provided documentation or evidence of actions taken (related to Annex 4)? <p>If the answer to all is “no” → Skip or flag the dimension</p>			
Criteria	Details	Assessment	HTA relevance
What techniques are used to evaluate patient characteristics?	Determine the methods or tools applied, such as stratified sampling, comparisons with data statistical tests for demographic representation, or diversity audits.	Provide examples of applied techniques and tools used.	Include (if documented) – HTA can assess this if the developer provides demographic analysis summaries. Avoids the need for raw data and supports assessment of bias.
Is there a document describing which patient characteristics are being assessed?	Verify whether the organisation has formal documentation identifying the patient characteristics being evaluated for representativeness.	Yes/No <i>If yes, provide documentation such as reports, data dictionaries, or audit plans.</i>	Include – Straightforward and very relevant. HTA “doers” can check for population transparency and demographic scope using developer-supplied documentation (Annex 4).
How are gaps in patient demographic representation being assessed?	Describe the corrective measures taken to address imbalances or biases, such as oversampling underrepresented groups, adjusting data collection strategies, or integrating external demographic data.	Provide examples of interventions, such as targeted data collection campaigns or changes to sampling processes.	Include (if documented) – Can be included if the developer discloses how they identified and addressed underrepresented groups. Important for evaluating bias risk in HTA.
Is there a document describing which disease characteristics are being assessed?	Verify whether the organisation documents key disease characteristics being evaluated, such as disease types, severity, comorbidities, or progression stages.	Yes/No <i>If yes, provide documentation such as reports or datasets describing disease-related attributes.</i>	Include – Clear and valuable for HTA. Understanding which disease types, severities, and comorbidities are covered is important. Can be reviewed without raw data.

What techniques are used to assess disease characteristics?	Evaluate whether techniques like cross-tabulation of disease variables, or consultations with clinical experts are employed to identify coverage gaps.	Provide examples or applied methods or tools (e.g., disease prevalence reports, clinical dataset comparisons).	Exclude – This requires access to detailed clinical data and statistical outputs. Not typically available to HTA teams, especially post-development.
How are gaps in disease coverage being addressed?	Describe measures taken to address gaps, such as targeted data collection for underrepresented diseases, prioritisation of rare conditions.	Provide evidence of actions, such as new collection protocols or integration of disease-specific data sources.	Include (if documented) – Include only if supported by summaries. Helps HTA assess if the dataset adequately reflects the full clinical picture intended by the DHT.
Is there a document describing which population coverage characteristics are being assessed?	Verify whether the organisation has documented key characteristics for population coverage assessment (e.g., geographic, socioeconomic).	Yes/No <i>If yes, provide documentation such as population representation policies, reports, or completeness guidelines.</i>	Include – Relevant for HTA to understand regional, socioeconomic, or setting-based generalisability.
What techniques are used to evaluate population coverage?	Determine whether tools like gap analysis, geographic mapping, or distribution modeling are used to ensure that the dataset includes all eligible subpopulations.	Provide examples of tools (e.g., GIS mapping) and their application outcomes.	Exclude – Statistical coverage modelling requires access to source data and specialist's tools. Not feasible for HTA without developer summaries.
How are gaps in population coverage being addressed?	Assess the strategies for resolving coverage gaps, such as targeted outreach, inclusion of external data sources, or adjustments to recruitment methods to better capture missing populations.	Provide examples of implemented solutions, such as augmented datasets or evidence of improved population representation.	Include (if documented) – HTA can benefit from knowing how missing subgroups were identified and mitigated – if shared by the developer in Annex 4.

ANNEX 6: Data quality criteria towards the use of AI

The use of AI		
Criteria	Details	Assessment
Does the organisation specify the AI algorithm used and its data quality requirements?	Verify if the organisation documents the type of AI algorithm being employed (e.g., supervised, unsupervised, semi-supervised, reinforcement learning) and ensures that the data quality requirements align with the specific needs of the algorithm (e.g. labelled data for supervised learning).	Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide the documentation detailing the algorithm and its corresponding data quality requirements, such as project plans, technical specifications, or data quality models.</i>
Is labelling required for the selected AI algorithms?	Assess whether the organisation has identified the need for labelled datasets for semi-supervised learning tasks, based on the objectives of the AI application.	Yes/No, <i>If yes, verify that the organisation has a documented labelling requirement, supported by use case specifications or project documentation.</i>
Are roles and responsibilities for labelling defined and documented?	Assess whether the organisation assigns specific roles (e.g., annotators, inspectors...) and responsibilities in the labelling process.	Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide supporting evidence such as organisational charts, tasks assignment documents, or job descriptions.</i>
Does the organisation employ quality control measures for labelling?	Verify whether the organisation implements systematic quality control for labelling, such as random sampling, stratified sampling, or full inspection.	Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide examples of quality control processes, inspection results, or error rate reports.</i>
Are labelling tools or platforms aligned with data security and compliance requirements?	Check if the organisation ensures that labelling tools and platforms support essential functions (e.g., metadata creation, traceability) and comply with data security and privacy regulations.	Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide examples of tool configurations, security policies, or compliance audit reports.</i>

<p>Is the organisation mitigating bias in labelled datasets?</p>	<p>Assess whether the organisation implements strategies to minimise bias in labelled datasets (e.g., diverse annotators, automated validations, bias audits).</p>	<p>Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide evidence such as bias mitigation plans, audit results, or annotator diversity reports.</i></p>
<p>Are labelling processes and datasets documented for transparency?</p>	<p>Verify whether the organisation maintains detailed documentation of the labelling process, revisions, and metadata for traceability.</p>	<p>Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide examples of documentation, including labelling logs, metadata schemas, or audit trails.</i></p>
<p>Does the organisation periodically review and update labelling specifications?</p>	<p>Check if labelling guidelines and processes are regularly reviewed and updated to align with evolving use cases and quality requirements.</p>	<p>Yes/No, <i>If yes, provide evidence of versioned guidelines, review schedules, or change logs.</i></p>

ANNEX 7: Cybersecurity checklist for use by developers and HTA agencies

ID	Checkpoint ¹	Description	Suggested Approach ²	Suggested Evidence	Reasoning	Reference source
General						
1	Security by Design (SbD)	The SbD principle shall be considered during the entire development process	Integrate security features into the system's architecture and design from the outset	Document outlining security features and design choices made throughout the development process	Integrating security into software from inception onwards aids in making it more secure. Trying to integrate security into existing software can entail major efforts and code rewrites and sometimes lacklustre security	ISO 11073-40102:2022; BSI TR-03161-2 "O.Arch_1"
2	Threat Modelling & Context Aware Security	Create a comprehensive threat model identifying potential threats and vulnerabilities, especially considering the usage scenarios of software and devices	Document the threat model and update regularly based on changes in the threat landscape, bearing in mind all available interfaces (BLE, USB,)	Threat model documentation, considered usage contexts and regular updates	Threat modelling helps prioritise defences against the most probable and impactful threats, it furthermore also required to establish the context in which the software will be used	https://owasp.org/www-community/Threat_Modeling , NIST SP 800-30; IEC 80001-1
3	Coding Best Practises	Follow secure coding guidelines, such as OWASP or CERT, and conduct regular code reviews	Establish & use secure coding practices and conduct code reviews	Code review logs and secure coding practice documentation	Reduces vulnerabilities in code such as buffer overflows and injection attacks	OWASP Secure Coding Practices; CERT Secure Coding, ANSM R37
4	Third Party Auditing	Conduct regular audits of third-party components and apply necessary updates promptly	Audit and assess third-party components regularly	Third-party audit reports and a log of vulnerability patches applied	Third-party components often introduce vulnerabilities that must be managed	NIST Cybersecurity Framework; IEC 62304 5.1.5 ; BSI TR-03161-2 "O.Arch_1", ANSM R6,R37

ID	Checkpoint ¹	Description	Suggested Approach ²	Suggested Evidence	Reasoning	Reference source
5	Open-Source Reimbursement	Provide a scheme to reimburse open-source projects that have been essential to the product	Donate or allocate a fixed amount monthly to the most relevant open-source projects used	Donation receipts or contribution trackers in repositories	Open-source software is paramount for most applications. However, maintainers often lack resources to handle all arising issues. Supporting them enables timely intervention to security issues.	https://www.redhat.com/en/resources/open-source-participation-guidelines-overview "Upstream First"
6	Security by Default	An application shall automatically be configured in the most secure way	If an application allows for configurations offering different levels of security, automatically launch to the most secure version	Configuration guides and default security setting documentation	Many users are not interested in security related settings, automatically offering the strongest security to them makes it more likely for them to use these settings	ISO 11073-40102:2022
7	Usable Security	Accept the human-factor to cybersecurity. Ensure security features are user-friendly, adaptable so users don't attempt to circumvent them	Follow usability principles for user-facing security measures. Educate users on implications of changing settings or following certain measures	Design prototypes with user feedback and usability testing reports. Report with reasoning for measures taken	Usability ensures that security features are used as intended. Accessible and user-friendly design reduces the likelihood of bypassing security mechanisms.	NIST SP 800-63B, ISO 9241-210
Authentication and Access Control						
8	Principle of Least Privileges / Role Based Access Control	Every user should only have the least amount of privileges they need to use the application	Implement role-based access control	Assigning permissions based on user roles	Minimizing privileges reduce risk of unauthorised access to system components, both through malicious internal as well as external access	ISO 11073-40102:2022
9	Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA)	Implement MFA for all sensitive data access points	Require MFA for sensitive data access points	MFA configuration documentation and user access logs	Additional authentication elements prevent malicious actors to breach a system through leaked or guessable passwords	BSI TR-03161-2 O.Auth_3

ID	Checkpoint ¹	Description	Suggested Approach ²	Suggested Evidence	Reasoning	Reference source
10	Session Management	Enforce secure session management with automatic logout after inactivity	Apply session timeout and automatic logout policies	Session timeout configuration documentation and session log files	Secure session management reduces the risk of unauthorised access from stale sessions	BSI TR-03161-2 O.Auth_9 - 16
11	Access Logging	Enable logging for all access events and regularly review logs	Implement and review access logging policies	Access log files and log review schedules	Logs provide an audit trail and help detect unauthorised access	ANSM R29,30
Data Protection & Privacy						
12	Secure Data @ Rest, Transit, Use	Secure data at rest, transit, and use involves encryption, access control, and integrity mechanisms to protect data during storage, transmission, and active processing	Rest: Data is only stored in encrypted form, only decrypted for use Transit: Data is only transmitted in encrypted form over secure channels Use: Use of TEE, SMPC or other approaches	Documentation of cryptographic mechanisms to facilitate encryption at all stages	Encryption of data in all stages ensures that security properties are maintained. Due to the additional effort this includes for "use" it is not strictly required for this checklist and shall be included where appropriate	NIST CSF2.0 PR.DS
13	GDPR compliance	Conduct regular privacy impact assessments and follow GDPR principles	Perform data protection impact assessments regularly	Records of data protection impact assessments and GDPR compliance documentation	Compliance with GDPR ensures that privacy risks are managed effectively	https://gdpr.eu/
14	Network Security	Secure all network communications with VPNs or encrypted protocols like TLS	Implement VPN or TLS for secure network communications	Documentation on VPN usage and TLS configurations	Network security is essential for protecting data transmitted over potentially vulnerable networks	ANSM R23-27, NIST SP 800-52 Rev. 2
15	Password Rules	Implement password complexity and rotation policies aligned with best practices	Apply password policies for complexity and rotation; Maintain cybersecurity usability considerations to	Password policy documentation and password configuration files	Complex passwords help prevent brute force attacks	ANSM R10

ID	Checkpoint ¹	Description	Suggested Approach ²	Suggested Evidence	Reasoning	Reference source
			prevent unreasonable password requirements (too lenient or too strict)			
Cryptography						
16	No Security through Obscurity	Rely on well-documented, tested and implemented security measures instead of relying on hidden self-made mechanisms	Utilise strong cryptographic mechanisms that are available through common libraries in programming languages	Documentation on security mechanisms in use	Obscurity of measures does not offer security. Reverse engineering is likely to happen and succeed. (Kerckhoffs's principle) Relying on mechanisms that are known to withstand attacks with every part known is considered more secure Kerckhoffs's principle	ANSM R3; BSI TR-03161-2 O.Cryp_2
17	Strong Cryptographic Algorithms	Use only strong, up-to-date algorithms like AES-256 and RSA-2048	Use the strongest currently recommended cryptographic algorithms	Documentation on encryption algorithms in use	Strong cryptographic algorithms protect against data breaches	BSI TR-03161-2 O.Cryp_3,4,5
18	Strong Cryptographic Keys	Implement secure key management practices, including rotation and access control	Follow OWASP key management best practices (https://cheatsheetseries.owasp.org/cheatsheets/Key_Management_Cheat_Sheet.html)	Key management policy and rotation logs	Protecting cryptographic keys is essential for data integrity and confidentiality	BSI TR-03161-2 O.Arch_3
19	Penetration testing	Conduct regular penetration testing to identify and mitigate vulnerabilities	Regularly perform internal and external penetration testing	Penetration test reports and remediation action logs	Testing helps identify weaknesses in cryptographic implementations and should at best be performed through a	BSI TR-03161-2

ID	Checkpoint ¹	Description	Suggested Approach ²	Suggested Evidence	Reasoning	Reference source
					combination of manual and automated testing	
20	Check vulnerability databases	Regularly assess the application against OWASP Top 10 vulnerabilities and CWE weaknesses	Follow OWASP and CWE standards. Integrate with Point 4 to ensure security of components listed in the SBOM	OWASP and CWE compliance reports	Adherence to these standards ensures that common vulnerabilities are addressed	ANSM R37
System						
21	Continuous Monitoring	Use appropriate level of real-time monitoring tools to detect and alert on potential security events	Set up continuous monitoring and alerting systems	Monitoring logs and alert response documentation	Continuous monitoring helps quickly identify and respond to security incidents	NIST CSF2.0 DE, ID.IM-02
22	Incident Response Plan	Develop and test a formal incident response plan	Create and test incident response procedures as well as creating regular backups	Incident response policy and test results	Having a response plan minimises the impact of security incidents. This includes recovery and backup measures and can include emergency access options if adequate	ISO/IEC 27035, NIST CSF2.0 RS, ID.IM-04
23	Secure Update Mechanism	Secure software updates with cryptographic signatures and version controls	Utilise secure update mechanisms	Documentation on update mechanisms and patch management logs	Secure update mechanisms prevent unauthorised changes to the application	ISO 11073-40102:2022
24	Error-Friendly Reporting Culture / Blameless Culture	Encourage open error reporting without fear of reprisal	Implement error reporting policies, clearly communicate & demonstrate that mistakes aren't penalised	Error reporting logs and documentation on reporting procedures	A culture of reporting helps identify and mitigate issues openly and quickly	DSPT v7, NIST CSF2.0 GV.RR-01, PR.AT-01,02

ID	Checkpoint ¹	Description	Suggested Approach ²	Suggested Evidence	Reasoning	Reference source
25	End-Of-Life	Create a process for securely decommissioning systems and sanitizing data	Develop and document end-of-life procedures	End-of-life documentation and data destruction logs	Secure end-of-life practices protect sensitive data from unauthorised access after decommissioning	ANSM, SK, BSI, NIST CSF 2.0 ID.AM-08

¹ Checkpoint = name of criteria to be checked

² Suggested approach = advice for developers on achieving said criteria